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The Carlsberg's DraughtMaster sustainability challenges in the draft beer industry, from decarbonization to waste management:

Insights from students in the COIL project between Drexel University and HWR Berlin.

A REPORT

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COIL project overview

The brewing industry faces increasing pressure to address its environmental impact, particularly in reducing CO2 emissions. A notable example is the Danish Carlsberg Group, which has set an ambitious goal of achieving zero CO2 emissions by 2030. To accomplish this, Carlsberg is exploring innovative ways to improve their CO2-free draught system called DraughtMaster. This project, which focused on sustainability in the brewing industry, asked students to analyze the risks and opportunities of such initiatives in a multinational context, with a specific focus on Carlsberg's strategy.

Seventy students, from both Drexel University and HWR Berlin, participated in this Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL) project. Divided into ten groups and trained in qualitative research marketing techniques, the students conducted empirical research and interviews with industry stakeholders, including bar owners and breweries, over several weeks in Germany and the USA. The project spans from October to November 2021, with first class taking place on October 12th and specific weekly tasks including preparing interview guidelines, conducting interviews, analyzing results, and presenting findings. Tools Used range from Google Drive, Google Docs, Zoom, and other tools selected by students for collaboration. Their findings were presented to the entire cohort on November 16th, concluding the project.

This COIL project was organized by the authors, Professor Sonja Klose (HWR Berlin) and Professor Daniel Korschun (Drexel University), with guidance from Vinicio Di Iorio (Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies and visiting researcher at Drexel during the 2021-2022 academic year).

Executive Summary

The report gathered insights from ten group projects focusing on the perception, benefits, and drawbacks of the sustainable alternative to traditional metal beer kegs: Carlsberg's DraughtMaster system. The report aimed to explore how the DraughtMaster, already implemented in European and Asian markets, could expand into the U.S. market and be further improved where it is already in use. Based on qualitative interviews with both consumers and business owners (B2C and B2B), key findings emerged regarding sustainability, cost, system practicality, and waste management.

Key Findings

- **Sustainability Concerns:** The DraughtMaster system, while designed to reduce CO2 emissions and water waste, raised doubts among both consumers and business owners. The main issue revolved around the use of plastic kegs, which many found contradictory to the broader movement away from plastic. Concerns were also raised about how effectively the plastic kegs are recycled, with some questioning whether this truly offers a sustainable alternative to traditional metal kegs (Group 4, 6, and 8).
- **Beer Quality:** A major point of concern was whether the switch to a plastic system would affect the taste of the beer. Taste is critical for consumers, especially in the U.S., where several interviewees mentioned they would only consider the system if there was

no compromise in flavor. On the other hand, some respondents were open to the change, as long as the beer quality remained the same or improved (Group 4, 7, and 9).

- **Operational Costs and Logistics:** For many business owners, the idea of switching to the DraughtMaster system was met with hesitation due to concerns about the upfront costs and retrofitting their existing infrastructure. Many had already invested in traditional keg systems and were reluctant to adopt a new one without clear evidence of long-term cost benefits. There was also a worry that switching distributors or systems could disrupt established relationships (Group 6, 7, and 8).
- **Consumer Interest in Sustainability:** Both U.S. and German consumers generally liked the idea of sustainability, but the use of plastic remained a sticking point. People wanted to know more about how much of the system was recyclable and what its actual environmental impact would be. Transparent communication about the long-term sustainability of the system is needed to address these concerns (Group 3 and 7).

General recommendations

1. **Address Plastic Waste Concerns:** Given the skepticism around plastic, Carlsberg should take concrete steps to deal with the plastic waste generated by the DraughtMaster kegs. Establishing a robust recycling program in collaboration with local governments or third-party recyclers could be a key part of this. Additionally, Carlsberg might consider exploring more sustainable plastic alternatives or ways to reuse the kegs in a circular economy framework. Transparent communication about what happens to the plastic kegs after use would help build trust with environmentally-conscious consumers (Group 7 and 8).
2. **Strengthen Communication on Environmental Benefits and Technological Support:** Carlsberg needs to develop a clear, comprehensive communication strategy that not only explains the sustainability aspects of the DraughtMaster system but also emphasizes the technological advancements behind it. Business owners and consumers alike need reassurance that the system's environmental impact is significant, particularly when it comes to reducing CO2 emissions and addressing plastic waste. Alongside this, Carlsberg should offer robust technological support to make the transition smoother for businesses. This could include remote assistance for setup, troubleshooting, and maintenance to ensure the system is implemented correctly and efficiently. Providing this level of technological guidance would increase confidence in adopting the DraughtMaster system (Group 3 and 7).
3. **Cost-Effective Adoption Strategies:** To ease the financial burden for businesses, Carlsberg could offer leasing options, flexible payment plans, or even a trial period to help businesses test the system. Presenting a clear long-term cost comparison between DraughtMaster and traditional systems could further alleviate concerns about upfront investment (Group 6, 8, and 9)

By addressing these concerns and following the recommended approach, Carlsberg can increase the likelihood of a successful U.S. market entry for its DraughtMaster system.

Group 1

Introduction

Carlsberg Group's DraughtMaster® (DM) aims to transform the traditional draft beer industry by offering a more sustainable system. With the use of plastic kegs and pressure modules, instead of metal and CO₂, this system is lightweight and small. For businesses, this means an easier transportation process. While traditional kegs with CO₂ pumps decrease beer quality in only a few days, the DM's CO₂-free system results in longer-lasting beer. As a result, businesses can offer a greater range of products due to lower costs from less replacement. The DM kegs can also be recycled, which prevents water waste that typically occurs during the washing process for metal kegs. Additionally, the CO₂-free nature of the DM is also more environmentally friendly.

The preceding value propositions have led Carlsberg to successfully introduce the DM system to the markets of Germany and a few other European countries. Carlsberg now aims to introduce the system to the United States. In doing so, the company faces a few challenges. There are many factors to consider before launching the DM to a completely new market. Cultural and social preferences differ from region to region and without comprehensive market research, there is a chance for Carlsberg to overlook these attitudes. It is important for them to understand both the direct and business consumer before introducing their product. Failing to do so could have adverse consequences for Carlsberg, such as low customer volume, budget conflicts, and negative ROIs.

The research questions necessary to understand the US market for Carlsberg's DM launch cannot be answered solely through secondary research. The reason for this is that DM is a completely new product. Although sales data and industry reports can be used to somewhat understand the market picture, this data is extremely limited. Sustainability within the beer industry is still a relatively new concept in the United States. There is not much data regarding beer preference and its relation to sustainable distribution. For this reason, we conducted primary research to obtain more precise findings for Carlsberg. The objectives of our research were to understand the perception of US consumers and businesses regarding the DM and its current components. Specifically, we took a qualitative research approach utilizing individual interviews. We then analyzed our data to present concise findings from our market research. Lastly, we use these findings to offer recommendations to Carlsberg regarding how to successfully enter the US market.

Methodology

For this research project, we conducted two business-to-consumer interviews in both the United States and Berlin, Germany, as well as one business-to-business interview in Germany in order to gauge the responses on the DraughtMaster from a variety of individuals involved in the selling of beer overall. For the B2C interview in the United States, we interviewed a 23-year-old from New York City and for the other B2C interview, we spoke to a 21-year-old from Munich,

Germany. Through these interviewees, we were able to capture information and reactions of the DM from everyday people who are not necessarily involved in the operations of the beer industry itself, but rather they are average and regular consumers of beer. Their thoughts on the DM are important in order to understand how the public may respond to an innovative and sustainable initiative in the overall drinking consumption culture around the world. Initially, we asked a variety of different surface-level questions that focused on their preferences related to beer, factors that affect their beer purchases and consumption decisions, thoughts on sustainability in the beer industry, etc. After introducing the DM, we prioritized asking questions that captured the interviewee's thoughts on the product's sustainable features including the plastic kegs, the barrels being CO2 free, whether this innovation can be a good step in making the beer industry more sustainable overall, if they would consider converting to the sustainable option instead of traditional metal kegs, etc.

For the B2B interview conducted in Germany, we spoke to a bar manager from a family-owned business in order to gain insight on the DM from a business standpoint, in comparison to the consumer perception from the B2C interviews. We wanted to gauge how a business would respond to this sustainable option after being introduced because businesses would essentially be the main buyers in the beer industry. This innovation has the potential to drastically change the beer industry, and it can affect businesses that use the typical steel keg system, so it is necessary to understand where businesses currently stand on the DM overall. For the beginning of the interview, we asked similar general questions to the B2C interviews, along with business-specific questions related to the selection of beer they sell, the reasoning or factors behind selling those respective beers/brands, the popularity of brands served, etc. To transition, we asked questions more focused on sustainability including whether sustainability practices of their beer suppliers are considered, if they would prefer to sell a beer brand that is mindful of their environmental impact, and their general experience/concerns with traditional steel kegs. After introducing the DM, we moved onto gathering their responses on the DM by focusing on their initial thoughts and concerns, overall pros and cons, along with asking whether they would replace their regular steel keg system with this new innovative alternative. Some other questions asked related to if this more sustainable option could be more attractive to consumers, their thoughts on sustainability in the beer industry, and how the DM can impact the beer industry as well. After gathering all of this information, our group along with the nine other groups partaking in this research project, entered our findings into a massive excel sheet. The sheet's purpose was to consolidate important information such as the type of businesses we spoke to, the job of interviewee, importance of tap to the business, customer base, price range of locale, process of receiving and distributing beer, cons of serving beer on tap, likes and dislikes of the DM, confliction between sustainability and using plastics, and possible solutions of the respective conflicts. From this sheet, we were able to summarize our findings and learn the results of the other groups' research as well.

Findings

The B2C interviewee from Germany is the only one of the three interviewees who knew the Carlsberg group.

One finding that we observed was the reasons behind why consumers in the US choose their beer vs why the consumers in Germany choose their beer. While both informants valued bottle design and the price, those in the US are heavily influenced by high alcohol content and taste. German customers value the taste of regional beers and traditional German beers, which is also supported by the B2B perspective of valuing where the beer comes from.

“No, there is still the regional aspect. The customers go there for regional and healthy products. I still believe that factor would outweigh. It is about the quality of the beer for the customers and the taste and not necessarily about the keg system.” (Interview B2B Germany)

Both the German and US interviewees acknowledged the importance of sustainability but were not strongly influenced by this when it comes to choosing their beer. Though, the German participant was more environmentally conscious in their decision to choose regional beers which had less of a negative impact on the environment.

“I mean if I’m being very honest it’s not up to me to convert to this sustainable option, because I obviously do not buy beer kegs like that. I buy it by the bottle and pint, but I would be very excited to see if some of the bars and restaurants that I frequent will make a shift to this more sustainable keg.” (Interview B2C US)

This response makes it seem as if they would be willing to make the change if it became more mainstream. As we aim to move towards a more sustainable lifestyle, more sustainable kegs could be at the forefront of the beer industry. In order for this to occur, someone needs to take charge and do so rather than waiting around to watch others make the shift first. However, from the B2B perspective, the focus is not on providing more sustainable kegs, it is rather about creating short and local supply chains to decrease the environmental impact.

“No, currently less attention is paid to this. It’s more the issue of sustainability in this way, that the beer suppliers are regional, and no long distances have to be covered for delivery. If you argue like that, then we do think about sustainability, but not necessarily about specific actions by the supplier that make the company look more sustainable. We don’t have supply chains that cross multiple national borders, it’s a 15-minute drive at most. That makes the whole thing more environmentally friendly.” (Interview B2B Germany)

The German B2C interviewee had no concerns about the use of plastic kegs in the DM system, as they supported the option of properly recycling them when finished:

“No, I don't. Because with watching the video and receiving the information from you, I got the feeling that, when the plastic kegs will be recycled, you get a better product out of this system, you have less rubbish and you don't have as much waste as before, so only good thoughts about that.” (Interview B2C Germany)

Though, both the B2C interviewee from the US as well as the German B2B interviewee are skeptical about the use of plastic:

“The use of plastic is a bit conflicting because plastic does take a long time to break down, even when it's recycled. But it may serve the design of the Draughtmaster better, so I'd understand why it's used.” (Interview B2C US)

“Then there's the plastic aspect. It may be recyclable, but no. I don't want fine plastic particles in my beer. The only thing I've seen that is still supposed to be an advantage, is that everything can be taken out of the barrel down to the last drop, but that's not a convincing point for me either, replacing the steel with plastic. I'd rather have no plastic particles in there. Besides, after all, the steel kegs are rinsed out and reused and not every single one of them is thrown away.” (Interview B2B Germany)

Moreover, we observed a difference between the customer and the business perspective regarding the general idea of the DM. Consumers are convinced that Carlsberg's new keg system will have a positive effect on the environment:

“I think it's a really good idea. The world is really going through it right now with excessive CO2 emissions and I think this alternative keg system would really make a difference if more businesses were to use it. Companies contribute a significant amount of CO2 in the environment, and I think it's great that a big brewery company is taking the initiative to become more sustainable.” (Interview B2C US)

“Yeah, so overall, I think, with the future in mind and with all the positive things it brings with it, it's a very great move forward.” (Interview B2C Germany)

On the flip side, the business perspective does not see any advantage in it and doesn't think it will change consumer preferences. Furthermore, he shows concerns about the costs attached with introducing a new system:

“Yes, rather concerns. After all, the barrels and keg system are already established, and everything is in place. I can imagine a large cost associated with putting this new system in place.” (Interview B2B Germany)

However, all consumers would like to try a beer from the DM to see if it has an influence on the taste of the beer.

“Yeah, you know I’ll have to try it out to see if there are any differences in the beer that comes out of each, but I think if there is a little to no deviation, I would be very inclined to have beer from the Draughtmaster as it is a sustainable practice.” (Interview B2C US)

Nevertheless, in the case of the German consumer it will not have an influence on the preferences.

“I would try it, just to know the difference, but I would still stick with my traditional hometown brands.” (Interview B2C Germany)

Recommendations

1) Prove to US consumers that there is no change in the taste of beer that comes out of a plastic keg with no CO2 pump when compared to a metal keg that uses a CO2 pump

In both of our consumer interviews, the main barrier to trying the DM for the consumer was the taste. Although neither currently consider sustainability during their beer consumption process, they are not opposed to it. If there is no difference in taste, they would be more inclined to choose the option that is more environmentally friendly. However, for this to happen, Carlsberg needs to prove to consumers that taste is not affected as they are currently skeptical of this.

Failure to do this can result in a misconception that beer from the DM system will not taste as good. Many beer consumers are loyal to their current, familiar taste of beer. Carlsberg needs to assure them that this will not change. If they do not successfully do this, there will be a hesitation from US consumers in switching to get their beer from a DM or even trying it.

There are a few possible ways for Carlsberg to prevent this. Below, are some ideas as well as potential implications of each:

→ *Provide free samples to consumers at bars/restaurants*

This method would come at little to no cost for the business because the sample size only needs to be a few ounces. Although they are giving away some products without earning sales, it could prove to consumers that there is no difference in taste. The customer lifetime value of a new customer acquired would exceed the small cost of the complimentary sample.

→ A commercial that shows real people (not paid actors) trying the same beer from both the traditional keg and DM

The costs of this method would be greater as they involve producing and airing a commercial. Depending on the network or platform that is utilized, the costs can vary. However, the benefit of this method is reaching a larger consumer group. Whereas free samples can only be given out to consumers at specific bars and restaurants, the commercial can be seen by more people. Even though they are not directly trying the product, they are likely to identify with other consumers similar to them. Hearing them share their opinions about no impact on taste can convince them to also try the DM out.

→ Advertising that emphasizes no change in taste along with the value proposition of a more sustainable system; Possible wording: “It’s your favorite beer done sustainably”, “Same great taste and it’s better for our planet”

If this wording is added to existing advertisements, then the modification costs would be minimal. There are no incremental costs associated with the addition. However, if there are also new advertisements created that incorporate these changes, the cost would be greater as they would involve new design and distribution costs.

2) Include more information when introducing businesses to the DM

From their initial introduction to the system, the business we interviewed raised many questions and concerns. Due to this, we believe Carlsberg needs to offer more information when introducing the system. The video currently provided is not sufficient enough. Adding more information from the beginning will prevent the common questions and concerns that arose. If a customer feels overwhelmed or confused from the very start, they are less likely to be open to the business idea. To prevent this, we have identified a few common questions based on our interview that Carlsberg can make sure to cover when approaching businesses. These questions surround three main topics: the recycling process, impact on costs, and plastic misconceptions.

- Recycling: Where should the empty kegs be stored? How often and by who will they be picked up?
- Impact on costs: How will implementing the DM system act to decrease costs or leave them unchanged for the business?
- Plastic misconceptions: How can businesses be sure that customers won’t stray away from their use of the DM due to perceptions on the impact of plastic on taste?

Below, are some ideas as well as potential implications of each for Carlsberg:

Provide one-on-one introduction/consultation services

One possible way for Carlsberg to introduce the product in greater detail that covers these questions is by offering free consultation services to businesses. During these sessions, they can explain the logistics of the system like the process of recycling. They can also provide a personalized cost analysis for the business to demonstrate a decrease or no significant change in cost. Both of these services would require staff that is able to either visit the business on-site

or meet virtually for a consultation. If Carlsberg already has the capacity to do this, there would be no additional cost. If they are not capable of providing these services currently, possible costs could include training or hiring costs.

Free beer tasting samples

Businesses also raised similar taste concerns direct consumers had. There seems to be a misconception surrounding the impact of plastic on taste. To fix this, Carlsberg can offer free samples of the product to businesses as well. Once they are convinced there is no negative impact, they are likely to share with their customer. The cost of free beer samples from the DM to management and employees would be very minimal. After, word-of-mouth marketing from them to their customers would be used, generating no additional costs for Carlsberg. It may also be a good idea to address the plastic misconception before others since it tends to impact both their B2B and B2C customers.

Free trial of DM or money-back guarantee

One final way for Carlsberg to allow businesses to better understand how DM can benefit them is a free trial or money-back guarantee. Through this, a business can try the system temporarily before switching over. In practice, when they observe no conflicts with their original concerns, they are likely to continue using the system. Research shows that free trial or money-back guarantees generally do not result in the customer returning the product or service. Once they own something, unless it holds dramatic faults, they are likely to keep it. This is due to the consumer behavior concept of ownership increasing value. So, the percentage of businesses who return the DM is likely to be low. Even those that do, do not pose significant costs on Carlsberg. The product only needs to be cleaned and can be reused or offered to a different business.

Group 2

Introduction

Sustainability as a whole is entirely too large of a concept, and a part of a much larger global responsibility that we all share in common, that is to give life back into this earth as it has for us. For a long period of time, sustainability did not exist as a concerning topic for mostly anyone who was not willing to be called some variation of a hippie, tree-hugger, or an environmental nerd. However, as people and businesses of today's society continue to shift their priorities and perspectives to the planet instead of profit, it has become in the best interest of most businesses everywhere to have a strong sustainability team that holds the business accountable for its impact on the planet and its natural resources.

For the majority of us, we learn about sustainability as soon as we are introduced to the widely-known phrase of "Reduce. Reuse. Recycle." As companies continue to grow their sustainability strategy for their organization, it is immensely imperative that they assess the knowledge of their target audience with relation to the value created by designing, implementing, and maintaining sustainable efforts to support product development. This is important and necessary to acknowledge because with alcohol consumption comfortably exceeding a billion every year, especially beer, there's also an increase in CO2 output into the environment. Fortunately, enough for Carlsberg and one of their newest products the DraughtMaster®, we were able to conduct extensive qualitative and quantitative research through interviews with alcohol consumers and businesses throughout the city of Philadelphia to survey the interest of prospectively launching the DraughtMaster® here in the United States. To further assess the potential impact Carlsberg can have with the expansion of the DraughtMaster® into the U.S. and Germany, we and our German counterparts conducted both B2B and B2C interviews for a deeper dive into the perspective of players in the market.

Methodology

For our business-to-consumer interview, we interviewed Lexi Wysocki, an Environmental studies major from Maryland, who used to work at a bar called The Wrap Shack. Something unique about Lexi was that she had an allergy to alcohol; however, this did not stop her from drinking sometimes. While this was seen as a con during the interview process, she still gave great insights into the process of serving the draft beer to customers. Another important thing to note about Lexi was that she was an Environmental Studies major so even though she may not be a huge drinker, she was passionate about the environment and therefore intrigued by the idea of the Draughtmaster. The interview started off with introductions and learning some background about Lexi and her experiences with beer. From there the conversation moved towards her actually serving the beer and then onto her thoughts about the Draughtmaster. Despite the interview being over Zoom we still were able to get some preliminary reactions about this new device. This interview was a great starting point for our project and helped us as we shaped the process for our following business-to-business interview. For the business-to-business interview, we interviewed Abbey Haas, a Communications major at Drexel University, who currently is a bartender at The Post. She was immediately so excited to speak to our group

and talk about her experiences working at this bar. Abbey has a minor in Environmental Studies which contributed to her knowledge of how draft beer can impact a business. Abbey expressed great interest in the DraughtMaster, saying that the only hurdle would be the public's acceptance of the new keg. However, she said with confidence that if this new keg had a great marketing strategy then there would definitely be major acceptance into the product. This interview was conducted in person at the Post, allowing us to have a behind-the-scenes look at the bar itself, as well as watch the kegs get delivered to the bar. This gave us more insight into the process from delivery to serving the beer to a customer.

Our German counterparts decided to interview the boss of Dicke Wirtin (Savignyplatz Berlin) and Luis Romero. The interviewee Luis Romero, was 23 years of age, and had just moved to Germany from Canada two months ago but is originally from El Salvador. It is important to note that the business Dicke Wirtin, has been around for 80 years whereas the businesses the U.S. group interviewed were around two years old. This wide age gap between the two businesses most definitely had an effect on the responses. The boss of Dicke Wirtin expressed how the German pub is mainly focused on serving German beer. They have branded themselves that way and have leaned away from foreign brands of beer. He was definitely very confident in the German brands that he serves at his pub and the methods of obtaining the kegs from wholesalers. Since Luis was new to Germany he was eager to go to many of the different pubs and try different beers. While he did already have a few favorites he was still very willing to try anything that came his way. When it came to sustainability he immediately stated how he believed more in ride sharing and does not buy fast-fashion brands anymore. As the conversation turned to the DraughtMaster, Luis offered a clear perspective on how this product would have a real impact on the consumers willingness to accept the plastic keg. The German group conducted both of their interviews over Zoom due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions in their country. Overall all the interviews proved incredibly helpful in creating our final presentation.

Interview questions:

- How do you feel about draft beer?
- How do you feel about companies intertwining their products/services with social responsibility?
- Do you think your place of establishment would benefit from using this type of product?
- What potential challenges do you think your restaurant or any other establishment would face when utilizing this product?
- From your opinion of working with different beers on taps, could you give a projected impact on telling the difference between taste with the metal vs plastic kegs?

Findings

#1 - Perceptions towards DraughtMaster (German & US)

With not forming any hypotheses before conducting both of the German and US interviews, there was not much to expect rather than hearing their genuine perspective on the execution on the launch of the DraughtMaster. Interestingly enough, one of the core findings that was brought to light after analyzing the interviews was that there were conflicting feelings about the

DraughtMaster from both sides. From the U.S. side of the project, our B2B and B2C interviews yielded information from the interviewees that point in the direction of being more open to exploring the idea of implementing a product like DraughtMaster into their business process. One of the biggest supporting details for that fact, for the US B2B interview at least, is that The Post already is somewhat environmentally conscious by only using biodegradable products like straws and napkins. So, while their customers are definitely on the more loyal side of knowing their beers and sticking with them, there is an opportunity for DraughtMaster to expand in the B2B context here in the US because they are somewhat already aligned with sustainable practices for their business, which also leads to another finding of ours with the need for more education about the product (DraughtMaster) and its beneficial impact. Whereas the U.S. interviewees were a bit more optimistic regarding how plastic contributes to increased positive sustainability efforts, there was no wiggle room in the German perspective to be introduced to the product because of their perception of the material.

From the German side, the general consensus was negative regarding the utilization of DraughtMaster. The main arguments made from their side pertained to the confusion of how using plastic would be good for sustainability and how it would be beneficial to their business overall outside of the fact that it would cause less CO2 damage and is a more size and environmentally-friendly container. In their B2B interview, the interviewee actually responded to their introduction of the DraughtMaster® by clarifying their concerns with the product by saying, "It's plastic again, where I actually want to get away from." Whereas the US thought the beer could taste better and lighter with the improved CO2 relationship, the German interviewee expected that the chemicals from the plastic would alter the taste of the beer for the worst and in turn negatively impact the Carlsberg's public perception. Overall, the general opinion about the DraughtMaster® contradicts between the U.S. and German perspective, but fundamentally, successful expansion could occur in both countries, however, much more education on the product life cycle and its impact on sustainability would be needed prior to making the decision to expand into those markets.

#2 - Different Ways of Reconciling the Conflict Between the Usage of Plastic & Sustainability

Another key learning that our group discovered that came from this project is the different ways of reconciling the conflict between the usage of plastic & sustainability. Through the interviews, we were able to gain a lot of different feedback regarding the usage of plastic. Plastic is not a very loved material in today's society as it causes pollution as well as is heavily damaging our oceans, therefore if plastic kegs are used the company should try their best to make sure they market the fact that the plastic will be efficiently and effectively recycled, otherwise it could cause backlash on not only the product but also the company. The upside to plastic however is its lightweight and has the same functionalities and capability as the current metal kegs available in today's market.

In the B2B interview, the person we interviewed mentioned that they liked the concept, however, was scared of how the market would react stating "So promotion, like if they promoted this product the right way, and marketed it, for lack of better. Oh, well, to the public. I think that that makes all the difference." They believe that there is a conflict, but they also think that plastic could be a good idea as it will break down faster than the current metal kegs. Overall I feel as though as long as the company makes sure they market the fact that the plastic will not

cause harm to the environment, their consumer base would be very likely to purchase this product.

#3 - Marketing the Product to Consumers

One of the most important findings that was discovered from this project was that no matter which country, the businesses would have to convince their consumers that this keg was the right direction to go in. This all depended on the philosophy of the interviewees and their own personal beliefs. The German interviewees did not believe in the fundamental philosophy behind the product, therefore they would not be able to market it. They did not feel that they would be able to convey the philosophy of DraughtMaster to customers. The boss of Dicke Wirtin (Savignyplatz Berlin) and Luis R. both would consider all alternatives to metal kegs before having to resort to the DraughtMaster. In general many restaurants want to move away from plastic in their daily operations and find other sustainable methods to utilize.

On the U.S. side, these interviewees, Lexi and Abby, were behind the idea of the DraughtMaster but knew it would take a strong campaign to make the public more receptive. “So I think if you were to give the bartenders just a spiel of why it might taste different and in those like most cases, it tastes better so like, why it might taste like that and like differences of pressurized co2. I think it would be fun,” said Abby. They knew education about the new keg would be most important. The metal kegs are very heavy to carry so they would much prefer the lighter DraughtMaster. Also on occasions the Post has run out of CO2 for the lines in the past, so a pre-pressurised system would benefit the restaurant greatly. DraughtMaster would need to be marketed the right way to ensure the community adapts well to the product, while understanding the purpose for it. However a negative would be that it would take time for the Post and its affiliated restaurants to incorporate this new method. “Because I think in a lot of restaurants, to see feasible change and tangible change actually happen, it takes a lot of pushback, because restaurants don't really like change, unless it's like benefiting them,” said Abby. Upper management would have to sign before the DraughtMaster was even mentioned to the public. The city of Philadelphia as a whole also does not recycle so this recyclable plastic, while good in theory, would not be overall beneficial. This finding shows how despite the cultural differences, consumers are the same in the fact that they need the proper education about a product before they are willing to accept it into their daily lives.

Recommendations

Based on our observations and insights made, we found that education will be the most important aspect in integrating Carlsberg's kegs to the US. Both customers and businesses must be educated in order for the product to not only perform successfully but for the brand to be well incorporated and further increase its brand awareness. Bars in the US such as The Post tend to use metal kegs and are not typically focused on practicing restaurant operations with sustainability at the forefront. According to an employee at The Post, sustainability is not prioritized due to convenience and poor restaurant procedures. “So here, I think it's interesting, because they'll (The Post), only buy certain straws or napkins that are like biodegradable, but then they'll use paper menus, and they'll use like other things that are just so unsustainable. Also, Philadelphia in general doesn't recycle. And we don't either...it's been frustrating for me personally, but I think for a lot of us, because it just feels so wasteful. And unfortunately, that's

the restaurant industry in general. Like it's, it's crazy how much waste I'd say we consume on a weekly basis and knowing that that is probably average compared to the rest of the restaurant industry” Carlsberg should include training videos and guides for restaurants to incorporate inoperations of the product and also create challenges and incentive programs for running a sustainable business.

By promoting and incorporating sustainable habits, more restaurants will find it more resourceful to utilize Carlsberg products. Regular customers tend to find sustainability an important value as well, as long as it does not disturb the quality of their desired products or price. That being said, promotion of sustainability to customers can be more favorable as corporate social responsibility is now being valued at a higher level and taken into consideration by the public. This can be seen through the many praises and even protests and public scrutiny presented in and out of social media in each industry. Particularly with restaurants, consumers tend to value places that show their care not only in the quality of the foods they serve but the overly procedures and operations of the establishments they dine in. That being said, education of the importance of sustainability promoted through restaurants can allow for a more favorable outcome for Carlsberg.

Promotion of the Carlsberg brand itself may also be a bit harder to incorporate as many consumers value local products and services in the US. According to a consumer for our B2C interview, most people tend to order “domestics" as there are a lot of local breweries in the Philadelphia area. However, if marketing and advertising highlights its sustainability and incorporates incentives, customers will be more on board.

When dining at restaurants or bars most love happy hours and sports related events. Happy Hour with Carlsberg would be able to shed light on who Carlsberg is as a brand, what they have to offer, and will later increase awareness through word of mouth. Bars specifically like The Post would be a great start as they are interested in not only conserving costs but also running operations more efficiently. As a fairly new business with more than one location, Happy Hours, and educational promotion would encourage good practices in and out of the industry. If bars or restaurants are unable to incorporate the Carlsberg plastic kegs due to traditional operations, affordability, etc. promotion should still be set in place.

Rather than using Happy Hour with Carlsberg, media and tv ads can be ran to promote sustainability as a whole or even promoting safety such as encouraging all to drink responsibly. It has been noted and observed that most beer and alcohol companies do not strongly promote/discourage drinking and driving. Though it may seem intuitive, this is still a major issue and can be indirectly the source of blame. By stepping up and creating a campaign around this, it will not only differentiate the company from its competitors but also feed the needs and interests of consumers through Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs (a desire for safety) and further promote the appeal of a brand not only caring about the products and quality they serve but more importantly the well being of their desired audience. This can be tastefully done, without the contradiction of not purchasing alcoholic beverages all together. Ad campaigns can still highlight the plastic kegs, pressurized CO2, and safety aspects; and still be able to appeal to a larger audience. Though operations may take a while to incorporate due to tradition; education and promotion is always valued, needed, and available to inspire others. That being said, Carlsberg can be the catalyst to revolutionizing the beer and restaurant industry.

Group 3

Introduction

Carlsberg Group is a globally operated brewery firm based out of Denmark with over 500 subsidiaries and a long history of creating craft beers. In 2011, the firm introduced the Draughtmaster system as an alternative means of beer delivery within a bar, pub or restaurant setting. The system is presented as a much more sustainable option stemming from a multitude of its innovations. Not only are there less emissions from the release of excess CO₂ and the elimination of insurmountable quantities of water waste stemming from the cleaning of traditional steel kegs, the system uses plastic kegs as an alternative as they are recyclable.

Carlsberg wants to ensure that the DraughtMaster launch within the US marketplace is successful. It becomes incredibly important to see if both the B2B and B2C markets see the benefits of switching to a plastic alternative keg system within the expectations and wishes of its implementation; this is especially the case in preparing to launch in an international market. If American consumer behavior and interest are not equivalent to the sales potential, it does not make sense to launch the product within the market. One must take into consideration several factors: the cultural norms of the market and the effect they have on potential consumer interest, current market conditions and the product's applicability to be effective within the marketplace. If American consumer and business owner behavior and interest are not equivalent to the sales potential, it does not make sense to launch the product within the market. Doing so in light of contradicting evidence would result in wasted time, energy and resources.

Rather than conducting research and compiling data via secondary sources, our team dove into discovering what insight real beer consumers and business owners had to say about the DraughtMaster system and if this would be of interest to them. Within this report, we will dive into the methodology used to gather our data, the information itself and our recommendations to Carlsberg.

Methodology

The project's main objective was to determine whether or not Carlsberg should expand its DraughtMaster[®] system to the United States, and if so, how they could best segment its value to ensure a successful launch. Our research sought to understand the opinions of individual beer drinkers as well as restaurant and bar owners who served beer on tap regarding their opinions on distributing, handling, and serving beer, and also their attitudes toward sustainable business practices. More specifically, we sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the perception (B2C and B2B) about introducing a plastic-based system (Draughtmasters[®]) to fight pollution and benefit the environment?
2. How do B2B and B2C customers reconcile the potential conflict between using plastics and being sustainable?
3. What do businesses that currently use Draughtmasters[®] (bars, pubs, and restaurants) think of the system?
4. What changes, if any, need to be made to Draughtmasters[®] if it is to be launched in the United States?

To do this, extensive qualitative research was conducted through one-on-one in-person interviews with consumers and business owners here in the United States, as well as in Germany, where the DraughtMaster® system has already been successfully implemented. The structure of the interviews followed an “hourglass” format outlined below, where both general and specific questions were asked to gauge the attitudes of our participants. The DraughtMaster® system was also introduced and explained during the “Concept Testing” stage, where we asked specific questions to understand the respondent’s reactions.

Two rounds of interviews were conducted - First, with specific beer-drinking consumers. Ten interviews were held here in the United States, and ten more in Germany, for a total of twenty B2C interviews. Various open-ended questions were asked about the individual’s drinking habits, their attitudes toward sustainable businesses, and their likes and dislikes about Carlsberg’s DraughtMaster® system. The second round consisted of eleven in-person B2B interviews (six held in the United States and five in Germany). Participants consisted of business owners, restaurant and bar managers, bartenders, and waiters and servers. We were most interested in their insights regarding storing and distributing beer, understanding what difficulties they had in doing so, as well as their opinions about environmentalism and sustainability. More specifically, we sought to understand how they would reconcile the conflict between using plastic kegs instead of traditional metal ones. Like before, we also introduced the DraughtMaster® system to understand their general perceptions, their likes and dislikes, and their willingness to implement it. All participant's responses were recorded and analyzed to examine the results and trends which are explained below.

Findings

Both consumers in the USA and Germany expressed an openness to the DraughtMaster®, as long as the taste does not lose its quality. During the B2C interview conducted in the United States, the interviewee expressed that “if {the DraughtMaster® system} allows the beer industry

to move forward in terms of sustainability and it does not detract from the taste of beer, I'd go right for it." The interviewee from Germany expressed the same thoughts and explained how *"the most important thing [is] how the beer tastes... expecting that it is cold {and} not too sparkling."* The interviewee went on to question how the DraughtMaster® system manages to keep beer cold in the plastic kegs. While our interviewees presented concerns relating to the taste, they made it clear that if there is not a difference, they would be interested in the DraughtMaster® system.

Consumers in the United States and Germany were skeptical of the process of the DraughtMaster®. The interviewee from the United States explained how the DraughtMaster® system would be new for brewers, restaurants, pubs, and consumers and, *"would be a learning curve and a shared experience for all."* Consumers in the United States seemed to doubt how single-use plastic is a better alternative to traditional kegs, which can be upcycled. Immediately after showing the United States interviewee a video explaining the DraughtMaster® system, they said *"I wouldn't trust a company per se just on their word of mouth, I would love to know the statistics behind why it would be more sustainable. Metal kegs can of course be used and reused and then also upcycled for so many other things, while a plastic keg at the end of the day is still plastic."* The interviewee from Germany also had doubts relating to the recycling process. This interviewee raised many questions, including *"How much energy does the recycling process cost? If you want to recycle every one of those small kegs or cans, is it really that more effective or efficient in terms of climate and sustainability to always recycle them after a single use?"*

They went on to explain how, *"you do not have to recycle metal kegs, you just have to wash them out and you can fill them up again."* The B2B interviewee from Germany felt that he could not convince his customers of the benefits of the DraughtMaster® system if he himself did not believe in the methodology. We found that both consumers in the United States and Germany are interested in understanding the research and data behind this new process to better understand its sustainability impact.

Businesses in the USA are unprepared to switch to sustainable options due to obstacles including time, money, and infrastructure, while businesses in Germany have already implemented sustainable options. Within our B2B interview, the owner expressed that they already practice sustainable measures, so he is not reluctant to adopt sustainable methods. The B2B interviewee had prior experience with the DraughtMaster® system and thought it was a great sustainable option for bars. Although, the interviewee from Germany posed similar concerns to businesses in the USA relating to price. When asked why the bar owner had decided against the system, he explained that they *"decided against the DraughtMaster® because first of all it's too expensive and steel kegs are more practical, you don't have to change as often."* While sustainability is a concern for many bars, restaurants, and breweries, we found these businesses to ultimately choose a more feasible pricing option over sustainability.

Recommendations

After examining the details of the interviews conducted in both the United States and Germany, it is clear that small changes to the process of the DraughtMaster® system could have exceptional results on the success of the product. One of the main concerns from both the United States B2C and Germany B2B interviewees was that the DraughtMaster® system would ultimately alter the taste of the beer. Since the system itself is made of plastic, one recommendation is to coat the inside of the system with a metal-like plastic. Recent research at Yale University has helped create bulk metallic glasses (BMGs). According to Kit Eaton BMGs, *"are alloys of metals where the structure is randomly arranged, giving them some of the*

material powers of glass, and some traditional metals...that can be blow-molded into shapes that are easily created using plastic or glass, but impossible using regular metals. They have the strength, resistance to impact, and durability of metal” (Eaton). If the DraughtMaster® system uses a BMG coating and goes through a thorough trial and error testing process, it is less likely for the taste of the beer to be altered.

Another concern brought up by the interviewee from the United States was the learning curve that restaurant and bar owners and employees will face when implementing the DraughtMaster® system. In order to avoid any confusion when using the new system, Carlsberg could potentially create a collection or series of training videos that will be provided to owners when the new system is purchased. The videos will provide an in depth explanation and tutorials on how to use the DraughtMaster® system properly. The video series will provide restaurant and bar employees with statistics of how the product is more sustainable. In addition to this, one recommendation that could be made is to alter the marketing campaign of the DraughtMaster® system. When marketing the product to potential buyers, it is vital that marketing campaigns include statistics and testimonials from users on how the DraughtMaster® system ultimately improves their business. Surveys could be filled out by users of the product before it officially launches and will be a part of the overall campaign. This will create an emotional appeal to prospective consumers and will add more meaning to the campaign overall. In terms of expenses, Carlsberg’s main outgoing payments would be for advertisements. Advertisements for the campaign could be seen across social media, streaming services, and television. For social media advertisements alone, a minimum monthly budget of \$300-\$900 should be set aside in order to place ads on all of the major social media platforms. If the budget allows, Carlsberg could work with a social media marketing agency to help boost the success of the campaign and integration into the United States.

This also leads to another recommendation that can be proposed. The DraughtMaster® system can be targeted to bars and restaurants in locations that practice sustainability so there is a cohesiveness to the brand. As shown in the findings, it was clear that businesses in the US were not ready to implement sustainable practices. It is a common trend that restaurant owners will choose the cheaper product to save money, rather than splurge on the more expensive and sustainable methods. If the DraughtMaster® system began its marketing efforts to restaurants and bars in places like Portland, Seattle, or Washington D.C., other cities will see its success and want to apply the DraughtMaster® system in their establishment. This will lead to favorable outcomes across the United States.

Works Cited

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Group 4

Introduction

The Carlsberg Group is one of the largest Danish multinational brewery companies in the world. The company was founded in 1847 and currently has operations in more than 50 countries around the world. A new eco-friendly system called the DraughtMaster was introduced in 2011. The main purpose of the DraughtMaster is to reduce the environmental impact by replacing traditional metal kegs with plastic kegs. The DraughtMaster is a smaller and lighter system that works to reduce CO₂ emissions, eliminate water waste, and acts as a recyclable product.

The Carlsberg Group has launched this innovative system in Germany as well as other European countries. Now, the question we seek to answer is whether this product should be launched throughout the United States, and if so, how. Market research is imperative to determine the best way to enter a foreign market. Without conducting research, the process of introducing the product runs a large risk of turning into a waste of resources, money, and time. Secondary sources, though helpful in assessing a new business environment, would not provide information with enough depth and specificity to be meaningfully helpful in this endeavor. Through collaboration of qualitative research, Drexel University and The Berlin School of Economics and Law came together to figure out the answer to this question. Specifically, students interviewed both business owners and consumers in the beer industry, both in-person and remotely to find out what they knew about the DraughtMaster and if they would be willing to endorse a system such as this one for a healthier and sustainable environment even if it came with a higher cost.

Throughout this report, Drexel University students will discuss the methodology used to conduct our research, the findings drawn from the information collected, and recommendations to the Carlsberg group regarding the potential for the system to be launched in the United States.

Methodology

Qualitative research is an area of market research that focuses on discovering the story and emotional process behind decision making. In approaching the question of bringing the DraughtMaster to the United States, the research team determined that finding a deep understanding of individual thoughts and feelings towards the system would be preferable to grasping a sense of broad trends. Conducting a series of individual interviews, both in-person and remotely, would be the most effective way to collect this detailed information. The larger international research team divided into ten groups; each group was tasked with conducting two business-to-consumer (B2C) interviews, and one business-to-business (B2B) interview, with the goal of conducting interviews with 30 individuals overall. The parameters for selecting candidates were broad, to better maximize the limited timeframe of the process. Roughly half the consumers selected should be from the United States, the other half from Germany – all should be known to drink beer at least occasionally. The criteria for the B2B candidates was simply that they should work with beer in some capacity; those interviewed had a wide range of occupations including bar owners, brewery employees, and servers. Over the course of several weeks, the ten teams conducted approximately 30 interviews globally.

All candidates were asked a series of progressively more specific questions about beer, sustainability, and after introducing the DraughtMaster, the Carlsberg initiative. Consumers were asked about their drinking habits, attitudes toward draught beer, attitude towards sustainability and - after an explanation of the DraughtMaster - their feelings towards the product, specifically if the use of the DraughtMaster would act as an incentive in their purchasing decisions. The B2B interview questions focused on aspects such as the general customer profile, importance of draught beer to the business, the logistics of receiving kegged beer from distributors, and their attitudes toward both their current draught system and sustainability in general. After being given an explanation of the DraughtMaster system, the candidates were then asked about their general perceptions of the product, their specific likes and dislikes, and if they would consider implementing the DraughtMaster in their place of work. All candidates were asked if they perceived a conflict between the use of plastic and sustainability in reference to the DraughtMaster, and if they could reconcile this conflict.

The findings from these interviews were compiled and shared across the team, using a spreadsheet to organize our collective data. From there, we began to search for significant trends, focusing on picking key pieces of information out of the loosely structured interviews and comparing the answers across all groups. Determining the attitudes towards beer, sustainability, and the intersection of the two across all interview candidates was an imperative step toward finding an answer as to whether or not - and if so, how - Carlsberg should launch DraughtMaster in the United States.

Findings

Having interviewed consumers from Germany and the United States, we have found that there was both a positive and negative interest in the DraughtMaster system. Focusing on the United States interviews with both consumers and business owners/workers, there was interest and excitement with reservations. The reservations that stuck out most prominently were a sense of worry around the taste of the beer, skepticism around plastic kegs, and how making the switch would impact daily operations.

In one interview with a United States consumer, there was a concern with the taste of beer among him and his potential friends. Hanif mentions when talking about friends, “if it didn't change the taste, then I would assume that they would purchase the same amount, if not even more.” Meaning that taste preservation means a lot to him and his peers. Many people in the United States interviewed were worried about the beer tasting differently due to the difference in CO₂. Despite worries about the beer being affected, many candidates reported that they would accept the new system if the beer did not change taste or if the taste was perceived as better. There was no hesitation from some to switch, but with an emphasis continued quality of flavor.

Another issue that was brought up was the use of plastic kegs. There were environmental and logistical concerns that were raised. During our interview with Doug, a bar owner in Philadelphia, he shared his previous negative experiences with plastic kegs. In his experience, plastic kegs have been too fragile, and are much more likely to crack or break during distribution and delivery. Doug also stated, “But in an effort to make changes to our existing system, I don't think that sustainability is enough.” Although he thinks sustainability in general is worth pursuing, it is not enough incentive to motivate him to completely change his system. He repeatedly summarized his feeling with the phrase, “If it ain't broke, don't fix it.” This raises concerns for DraughtMaster and how many people in the United States actually care and have the ability to recycle.

In the other interviews conducted by classmates, there was also a concern that “plastic is a horrible material.” There was skepticism about how great plastic really is for the environment. In the interviews, it seemed like the two main focuses were the taste of the beer and disdain of another plastic item on the market. The taste of the beer seemed to be a deciding factor that can be easily proved. However, changing the stigma of plastic products and not only debunking that they are not bad, but good would prove more difficult.

Another obstacle that we encountered was making the switch from metal to plastic and how it would affect customers and businesses. There was a lot of worry about learning curves in the industry. Teaching employees this new keg and how to work it would take time and money. These kegs would also have to coexist with metal kegs because as one business owner stated that he believes consumers prioritize taste and origin over sustainability. On the other hand, there was a positive point due to the heaviness of the metal kegs. An idea was brought up that a more diverse population in strength would be able to handle the kegs instead of large men due to the lightness of DraughtMaster.

Recommendations

The main issue Carlsberg now faces is incentivizing businesses to switch to the DraughtMaster. The DraughtMaster has many benefits, however businesses aren't always open to implementing change. From the interviews conducted, it is noticeable that both consumers and businesspeople want to encourage sustainability in the United States, but switching over the system will be a time-consuming process that not everyone is eager to go through.

Though many consumers love the idea of this product, they do not know the behind the scenes of what it takes to handle businesses. Business owners know what their consumers already like and are happy with what they already provide for their customers. What incentive do the businesses have when they are already making money? We suggest that Carlsberg should develop a plan to start small with their proposal to businesses in the United States, beginning in regional markets with more positive attitudes toward sustainability and cautiously expanding from there. Ideally, everyone wants to help the environment, but not everyone takes their time and efforts to follow through with this. Implementing a large-scale launch, or even a launch in an unreceptive market could result in a waste of time and resources, and hinder expansion into the rest of the country.

Carlsberg should conduct more research into cities that already have greener values and are more open minded to sustainability before they decide to launch in the United States. There are many small towns that would appreciate this product idea; however the appeal is not universal, and some trial and error is to be expected in the process. The greenest cities in the United States are located on the figure on the right. Carlsberg should familiarize themselves with these areas so they can implement their product into the optimal markets and if they succeed, then try to branch out. By conducting further research and testing the product in different areas, Carlsberg will be able to properly determine whether their product is feasible in the United States. Using such research will help them reduce costs, and increase their profits in the long run.

Group 5

Introduction

For this project, teams from Drexel University and the Berlin School of Economics & Law analyzed the DraughtMaster and the feasibility of this system being introduced into the United States. As the DraughtMaster is a plastic keg, we found a few general problems with this innovation. One is that there is a contradiction between plastic and sustainability. When plastic is produced, CO₂ emissions go into the air. Another issue is that the system is very complex and bars and restaurants are used to using an aluminum keg. As these are just a few issues we originally found, we will present a few others we discovered from interviews we conducted.

Each team was tasked with developing interviews to be conducted with consumers of beer and business owners that serve draft beer to gain their perspectives on this innovative technology, and its ability to achieve sustainability. We were able to gather concrete evidence through our interviews which we will present later along with extensive research about the DraughtMaster.

By gathering both information from our interviews, and from Carlsberg, we were able to form a better understanding as to what are some of the key issues with this new innovation. We needed to have a clear understanding of what the DraughtMaster was before going into our interviews so we could clearly explain this process to our interviewees, as well as be able to form our own educated opinion. Conducting interviews allowed our class to get up-to-date information from bar owners and beer-drinking consumers about what their personal experience has been like, and gain their insights about the innovation. Conducting both primary and secondary research allowed us to relate the information we gathered from our interviews back to the information we gathered from first researching the DraughtMaster. From our research, we concluded that it would be feasible to bring the DraughtMaster into the United States. But, we will discuss throughout this paper some suggestions we have for how to approach this as we do have some concerns about the innovation as it currently stands.

For this analysis, Professor Korschun (Drexel) and Professor Klose (Berlin) formed teams with students from Drexel and students from Berlin who collaborated as to how to organize this project. From the two classes, there were a total of 10 teams who completed and worked on the project. Our team consisted of 4 Americans and 3 German students. After establishing our code of conduct and team roles, we started thinking about who we would interview for our B2C interviews and B2B interviews. We conducted both B2C and B2B interviews to get perspectives from both beer-drinking consumers, as well as businesses who serve tap beer and have a keg system. As we are trying to see if this innovation would be feasible in the United States, it made logical sense to conduct interviews to get perspectives from people who actually work with kegs daily, and who would actually be using the DraughtMaster in their businesses.

Methodology

For our B2C interviews, we decided to interview one person from the United States and one person from Germany. For our first B2C interview, we chose a 61-year-old business consultant from America. We decided to interview him because our teammate knows him well, and knows he loves tap beer, and has a very specific beer he likes. For our second B2C interview, we chose a 26-year-old female Marketing Manager from Berlin, Germany. We wanted to get a perspective from someone who lives in Germany and also enjoys tap beer. Interviewing someone from the

United States and Germany, allowed us to see what similarities and differences there are among beer drinkers in each country, as well as the general consensus about sustainability. Before having the actual interview our team created discussion guides to organize the flow of our interviews and make sure we were touching on all key points. First off, we created an overall goal for the B2C interview. Our goal was to gauge the interest of beer consumers in terms of introducing a sustainable keg, and how they would respond to this innovation. We then divided our discussion guide into sections: The set-up, Introduction, General Beer Consumption, Bar experience, Introduction of Carlsberg Group Innovation, and Final Decision. Some of the questions we asked were, how do you distinguish the quality of beer? What is your opinion of replacing aluminum kegs with plastic kegs, and what does sustainability mean to you? We also got their overall impression of the Carlsberg keg and if they would recommend this innovation to bar owners.

Our class conducted a total of 10 B2C interviews in the United States and 10 in Germany. After we conducted the interviews, each team was assigned to do a qualitative analysis of another group's B2C interviews. The goal was to gather an in-depth understanding of the participant's perception, reactions, and suggestions about the DraughtMaster system. We looked for similarities and differences among our interviewees in terms of their openness to the innovation and their stance on sustainability. Our analysis allowed us to see that many people had a positive reaction to the idea of a more sustainable keg. About 50% of the participants liked that the plastic kegs are recyclable and more convenient to move around. A 25-year-old female interviewee from Philadelphia stated that it is better than metal kegs and would not mind paying extra for a good beer. However, there are concerns about the difference in taste and quality.

For our group's B2B interview, we interviewed a representative with 7-years of bartending experience. He is the Director of Operations for a bar in the United States named: Casey's Public House in Newtown Square, PA. Our goal through this interview was to gain this representative's perspective on the DraughtMaster technology, given their experience with keg beer, since we were tasked with deciding whether Carlsberg should enter the United States' bars and restaurants with their plastic keg system.

The interview developed by our team was structured into different sections which first included a set-up of the interview where permission was asked to record the conversation for purposes of transferring the audio to a written transcript for analysis. From there, the participant was asked about his background in the bar industry which was needed to qualify his expertise and eventual opinions about the DraughtMaster technology implementation into bars across the United States. After completing the set-up portion of the interview, the representative was asked about details of Casey's Public House business. Questions included from this section are as follows:

- What types of beer do you have on tap?
- Describe the importance of tap beer to Casey's business?
- Can you please describe the process of how your (tap)beer system works?
- Is draft beer more popular than bottles in your bar?
- Can you explain the process of tapping a beer and changing a keg for the bar?

The interviewee was then asked his personal opinions on sustainability and the importance of sustainability to Casey's business. The conversation transitioned to an introduction of the Carlsberg DraughtMaster technology and his opinions of this new system. Example questions from this section are as follows:

- What do you think a more sustainable keg would look like?
- What is your opinion of replacing aluminum kegs with plastic kegs?
- What do you think about this innovation? Likes vs. Dislikes?

- How do you think implementing this keg would affect your business operations?
- What concerns do you have about the Draughtmaster?

The interview concluded with overall impressions and a final decision from the representative where he discussed if he would implement this keg technology into his business.

Our B2B interview described in the prior paragraph totaled 52 minutes in length. The representative provided insight from the front of the house (bartending) and management departments which is important for DraughtMaster and its potential implementation into bars across the United States. Our group was made aware that Casey's Bar located in Newtown Square and Berwyn are family businesses where draft beer is most popular and preferred; each location has 12-20 taps for draft beer. When asked about current issues in the bar industry, the representative stated, *"The major struggle is people being able to move the physical keg. It's heavy... Getting the other keg back into a place where the old one was, and moving heavy stuff around is time-consuming...It's kind of just a process that I feel like there could be ways to eliminate that."*

After viewing the youtube video description of the DraughtMaster technology, the representative provided the following impression: *"The DraughtMaster, definitely a solution in that sense, with the plastic being a lighter material, and a little more portable than the regular keg ... I think it's a great solution. I mean, they're lighter, they're easier to move around. I think that is good. I don't see anything. I'm not opposed to it... The only issue would be that it's smaller than a regular one."* It is important for DraughtMaster to highlight its lightweight technology as a solution to current keg technology given the response our representative provided.

After conducting our B2B interviews, our class filled out a B2B analysis excel sheet that focused on a few different aspects like the general background of the interviewee, importance of tap to the business, their customer base, likes/dislikes of DraughtMaster, and if they see a conflict between sustainability and using plastics. Each group analyzed another group's interview, to eventually have 10 interviews filled out in this table. We were able to then compare each interview and gather key findings which we will explain next.

Based on the 2 B2C interviews our team conducted, as well as the rest of the class's interviews, it is concluded that overall sustainability is important to Americans, however, they don't have the resources set in place to be sustainable. Our American interviewee stated that as he is getting older, he doesn't believe that having this sustainable keg would make a difference in terms of going to a particular bar that has this keg. He emphasized that there needs to be more research done to see how profitable and impactful it would be for a restaurant. Germany happens to be more sustainable but would not invest in this system. Our German interviewee points out that trying to make the beer process sustainable might not be as appealing to consumers, since beer consumers don't think about sustainability. They are more reserved about the idea by questioning the price difference and the desired experience.

Findings

After analyzing and reviewing other teams' B2B interviews, there were common themes and concerns for the DraughtMaster that should be highlighted. We got a consensus that bars and restaurants would be less likely to invest in the system, while breweries would be more open to the idea. A bar manager from Munich, Germany expressed that he has concerns about the cost of implementation of this technology in his bar. He assumed that his business would have to replace his current draft system to make way for the DraughtMaster. A general manager from a bar located in Quakertown, PA expressed similar concerns in the following quote from her interview: *"Okay, yeah, I know, restaurants would like to know what that cost would be upfront."*

Because a lot of them don't necessarily have room for a lot of new equipment. Or they have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating. But that cost specifically to restaurants right now is a little scary, especially if you have to bring in a whole new system.” A business owner from Potsdam, Brandenburg, Germany provided the following quote which clarifies for the two prior business owners: *“Implementing the DM depends on the brewery and the cost and effort. The owner of the business chose to implement the DM in some breweries because it is more financially feasible, and also it allows him to provide a larger variety of beers on tap. Traditional kegs are more useful for bars where beer is sold in large quantities. They are cheaper per liter and don't have to be replaced as often.”*

Another key finding is about the recyclability of plastic. A waiter from Germany explained in the interview how he understands that plastic is difficult to recycle, and he prefers the reuse system which works better with metal kegs. Specifically, he stated, *“Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is recycled.”* The interview did express that if Carlsberg can make the plastic keg reusable the same or more times compared to a metal keg, then this innovation might be successful. Another interviewee our class had was a family-owned restaurant in Germany. They had similar doubts about the plastic keg. They were uncertain of how to properly dispose of the plastic kegs when they were finished. They said, *“But where does all the plastic go after the keg is empty? The kegs take up a lot of space. Do you have to dispose of them yourself?”*

A third key finding and theme from the majority of the B2B interviews addressed concerns with the implementation of the DraughtMaster technology in their respective businesses. While many of the business representatives found the technology and kegs to be innovative and interesting, they were skeptical about the investment needed to install the DraughtMaster technology into their bars. A general manager from a bar in PA highlighted these concerns while stating that restaurants may be open to the idea of the DraughtMaster technology but with businesses now open after their prolonged closure, they are in survival mode and may not be willing to take on the project of implementation during this busy period. A bartender from Ravensburg, Germany stated *“But I don't know if the installation is that easy as promised, I am a bit skeptical and I have to employ the new system.”* Of the 10 business representatives interviewed for this project, 6 directly expressed they needed further information about the installation of this technology in their bars.

Recommendations

Our first recommendation would be to target breweries first. Many of the interviewees expressed that this innovation would be better targeted at breweries specifically because of the cost aspect. As many bars and restaurants already have aluminum keg systems and understand how they operate, implementing this new innovation would mean learning a whole new process, training all staff, and an initial high cost for a smaller keg. Breweries can also reuse the plastic kegs and turn them into something else or remake the plastic kegs for future use. Restaurants and bars cannot be focusing on this as they have other operations to be concerned about, and the investment they would be making just solely on tap beer would be a lot. It is also clear that they might not want to do this because it is an entirely new system that they don't know anything about yet which would take a good amount of time to learn. Therefore, we would recommend targeting breweries first as they are the producers of beer and would be more willing to invest in that kind of system.

Our second recommendation would be based on our findings on the problem of recycling plastics. Carlsberg needs to make sure the recycling process is followed through till the end to ensure that the plastic kegs are being recycled properly and efficiently. We recommend

providing a thorough plan on how to do so. When looking at the Carlsberg website, there are videos available that mention how to change a flex 20 keg, yet it only says how to change the keg not how to recycle or what to do after the keg is done being used. Specifically, in the flex 20 keg video, it just says “discard”. We believe having a more in-depth explanation of the afterlife of the plastic keg would be beneficial for The Carlsberg Group as they can clearly show what they are doing to make sure this plastic keg is being recycled properly, and how investing in this keg will make a positive impact on the businesses and the planet.

Finally, to address the concerns of implementation, we feel that Carlsberg should include information about the installation process of this technology in its marketing materials and pitches. This could help ease business owners’ concerns which will lead to an open-minded approach from businesses when weighing the decision of whether to implement the DraughtMaster into their bars. We also recommend that Carlsberg should include testimonials from current clients that have gone through the implementation process which could provide insights into the process. If Carlsberg finds that education of their implementation process does not help, they could waive the upfront installation costs to help sign-on accounts. This will show they care for their business partners which will create upfront trust in the business relationship. Carlsberg could also help clients install the technology as a courtesy, so that is one less thing the businesses have to worry about.

Group 6

Introduction

The market for beer in the United States is expansive. We are exploring the possibility of implementing Carlsberg's DraughtMaster Keg system into the United States as a way to better serve those who drink beer in an eco-friendly and sustainable manner. According to the Statista Research Department, the U.S beer market is expected to grow to over \$140 million in revenue by 2025. For Carlsberg, finding customers is not the problem, the problem lies in understanding the landscape of an unfamiliar territory.

What are the systems in place that distribute draft beer? What are Americans' attitudes concerning sustainability? What factors do restaurant/bar owners consider important in efficiently operating their business? Our task revolves around any insights we can garner from these questions and more. We will be evaluating whether or not a new system driven by sustainability would be a viable fit under current market conditions in the United States.

Methodology

We conducted qualitative interviews with consumers and business owners to inform our approach in bringing DraughtMaster to market. We wanted to ensure that our interviewees were able to provide relevant information that would be useful to this study, because of this, consumer interview subjects were largely young individuals who go out often with frequent drinking habits. This added credibility to the interviewee's responses.

Our questions were drafted beforehand, although the interviewer was allowed to ask follow-up questions that were off the script, and tangentially related questions when they believed it would be helpful. We wanted to create as much of a freedom-oriented environment as we could, such that it didn't alter the interviewees' honest answers just because they knew they were being recorded.

All interviews were structured thoughtfully. For the interview with a consumer, we began with some broad questions about the subject's background, general drinking habits, and their thoughts surrounding sustainability. From there, we explained the concept of the DraughtMaster, and provided an audiovisual aid for the subjects to better understand how the unique system differs from traditional kegs. We ask questions to hear the participants' thoughts on the system, including any reservations that surfaced when it comes to rationalizing the use of plastic in the DraughtMaster.

For the interview with a restaurant/bar owner, we followed a similar structure. However, we were able to ask questions concerning their current draft beer system, the operations of their establishment, and their thoughts about implementing sustainable practices. This was of the utmost importance in evaluating the attitudes and trade-offs that they use in helping run an actual business. To Carlsberg, restaurant and bar owners are the customers.

The interviews were recorded, transcribed, and then analyzed from an aggregated data set that included other classmates' interviews. We categorically "coded" responses by analyzing the transcription and pulling out quotes that showed what subjects liked/disliked about the DraughtMaster for example. Many responses were coded into this data set, which allowed for a large and diverse pool of interviewees to learn from.

Findings

Across the board, businesses were generally intrigued by the light weight of the Draught Master kegs. A director of operations at a bar in Berwyn, PA was very receptive of the design. They noted, *"I think it's a great solution. I mean, they're lighter, they're easier to move around. I think that in itself is good."* Other employees or bar owners echoed similar sentiments, highlighting the fact that traditional kegs made out of aluminum or metal are heavy and hard to handle. The fact that DraughtMaster kegs were made out of plastic and were not only lighter but easier to transport and deliver was a big plus.

On the other hand, some bar workers/owners were a bit hesitant to embrace the system simply because it's new design would require replacing the existing infrastructure. This is embodied succinctly by a *"If it ain't broke, don't fix it"* mindset, quoted by a business owner in Philadelphia. A beverage director for another Philadelphia-based chain also had to reconcile the practical effects of implementing the DraughtMaster, stating that, *"it would need to be a complete overhaul of the entire system though."* These quotes set forth the idea that while sustainability efforts are often desirable to business owners, each has their own unique threshold for how far they're willing to go.

A general manager of a family-run business from Quakertown, PA felt like the costs may outweigh the benefits as well. Bars and restaurants *"have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating"* and *"that cost specifically to restaurants right now is a little scary, especially if you have to bring in a whole new system"* As we'll discuss later in the report, this may point the finger back at DraughtMaster that the company needs to prove it's worth even more in American markets.

A key finding in both business and consumer attitudes towards DraughtMaster is the negativity associated with utilizing plastic in the system. Many consumers expressed either a conflict of the idea of sustainability with the use of plastic or a general dislike of plastic material overall. Doubts were presented about the recycling practices of businesses and who would truly be able to keep them accountable. This may be owed, at least in part, to the lack of clear and consistent recycling infrastructure overall in the United States. One business owner directly on the city's programs. *"Philadelphia's not well known for its recycling programs that they're doing...You know, the question is how much stuff actually gets recycled anymore?"* These types of attitudes represent problems for bringing the DraughtMaster system into U.S. markets. In light of this, we've deliberated among a few recommendations that Carlsberg should think about before executing internationally.

Recommendations:

First off, Carlsberg should address the elephant in the room clearly and concisely, which is: What happens to the plastic kegs after they've been used? Given the fact that we found consumers and business owners were hesitant to embrace the use of plastic in the system, we believe that developing a communications based campaign for the DraughtMaster could be advantageous to introducing the system to businesses in the states. The communications should outline what to do with your keg once it is used, and furthermore, what if sent back to Carlsberg, what they do with the material. Of course this only works if a clear recycling plan is feasible in the states, and they're willing to invest in some sort of infrastructure to achieve this. The payoff might be worth it though for business owners and consumers alike to have clarity of mind that their actions are sustainable.

In the same vein as the communications campaign above, another recommendation would be to communicate further how the reduction of CO2 and water waste offset this use of plastic. Many interviewees have negative connotations of plastic, and restaurants have made efforts in different ways to reduce the amount of plastic used in their establishment. One Bar manager noted *“Nowadays we are trying to distance ourselves from plastic, plastic straws are banned and now we want to exchange the barrels for plastic too?”* Although this was quoted from an establishment in Germany, not the United States, it illustrates the point well. Similarly, many states have already banned single use plastic bags and legislation is continually ongoing. Because of this highly negative connotation with plastic, Carlsberg should be clearly explaining to their B2B customers how much the CO2 and water waste reduction make up for.

Another recommendation that would reduce the friction of implementing DraughtMaster in the United States as well would be to ensure that it could somehow fit into a bar/restaurant's existing tap infrastructure. As noted in the findings section above, restaurants may be hard pressed to justify replacing their whole draft beer/keg system with a new design, no matter how innovative. The costs just simply outweigh the benefits from a business perspective. This is incredibly important to keep in mind in current times, when restaurants are already struggling to stay afloat after the pandemic. Business owners may be more receptive to the DraughtMaster if they're able to integrate it easily into their current system. While we're unsure how feasible this is, addressing this concept head on in communication or sales campaigns should absolutely be a focal point. The *“if it ain't broke, don't fix it”* mindset can be pervasive, especially in an industry with tight margins as is.

With these recommendations in mind, we hope that Carlsberg can garner some valuable insights about whether or not it would be truly beneficial to introduce the DraughtMaster into the United States.

Group 7

Introduction

With more attention drawn to climate change in recent years, many companies have been making the move to greener resource use through recycling and renewable energy options. One of the world's largest beer companies, Carlsberg Group, have implemented their own initiative to reduce their environmental impact. They came up with the Draughtmaster, which alters the traditional beer delivery system by replacing metal kegs with plastic kegs and utilizing the circular economy system. This system not only reduces environmental impact but also provides organizational efficiency. Benefits of this system include: easier handling of kegs because of the decreased size and weight by being plastic rather than metal, being able to recycle the plastic which reduces waste involved with cleaning traditional kegs, and preserving the quality of beer for a longer period of time due to lack of CO2 emissions. Carlsberg has launched this system in Germany and other European countries and is looking to see if it is a viable system that could be adopted by customers in the United States. Through a series of interviews with B2C customers and B2B customers, we have gathered general opinions and thoughts on sustainability in general and in regards to Carlsberg's new Draughtmaster system.

Methodology

In order to gather opinions on the Carlsberg DraughtMaster System, we felt that it was most appropriate to conduct interviews. With an interview, it would allow for us to gauge opinions on the new system, as well as on sustainability as a whole. Interviewing two individuals was the most optimal way for us to gather qualitative research.

The first step in conducting the research was to segment our different audiences. For simplicity purposes, we chose to divide our findings into two: B2B and B2C. We felt that this division was the best way to fully understand our findings and gauge the opinions of a wider audience. It also best suited the industry. In the beer industry, consumption is both by the individual (consumer) and by groupings (business). Since beer can be purchased and consumed in both settings, we thought that it would affect findings. Thus, we chose these two segments.

The next step was to write the interview questions. Starting with the B2C interview, it was needed to first understand the individual. The first set of interview questions revolved on who the individual was. Questions that were asked related to age, occupation, hometown, and major (if they were a student). With these baseline questions, we could get a foundation and an understanding of who the consumer was outside of the interview setting. It was also beneficial to gather this information for segmentation purposes. For example, if multiple B2C interviews are conducted, it is important to draw the pattern between sustainability attitudes among students, professionals, elders, etc. These demographics paint a better picture on how the general audience would respond to the DraughtMaster System.

After these initial questions, we then asked what the individual's sustainability habits were. Again, it provided background context that would help understand their attitudes to the Carlsberg system. Once that understanding was established, we transitioned to asking about attitudes towards sustainability in the beer industry, then to introducing the DraughtMaster System. When introducing the new system, we made sure that we gave all the information we

had. We included an educational video that explained and visualized how the new system worked. From there, the individual was able to gauge how they felt about the new system.

The B2B interview was outlined in a very similar fashion. We started with gathering background information: what kind of business it was, how long it had been established, location, and general demographics of usual customers. Afterwards, we followed the same pattern as the B2C interview. We gathered data on the overall attitude towards sustainability, then transitioned to the role sustainability plays in the beer industry, and then finished with the DraughtMaster System. Questions in this interview were more pointed to shipping and delivery, as it is a very relevant part of running a business. Other questions included storage, recyclability, and how it affects price.

Overall, conducting a B2B and B2C interview was the best method to gather qualitative data. In conjunction with a recording of the interview, we were able to go back, draft a transcript, and use the transcript to begin analyzing findings.

Findings

Our interviewees for both our business to consumer and business to business interviews were residents of the US which is notable because of how those in Berlin's answers differed. The most obvious issue that surfaced while conducting the interviews is the lack of the overriding information needed by not only the consumers but the business as well. While many businesses were intrigued in the idea of the DraughtMaster System, they were skeptical of the added costs that seemed to be neglected by Carlsberg. *"Potentially? Sure. I don't see why not. I don't see it having any negative effects. But it would really just mainly be if it fit into our system. And you know, the cost of that is the main thing."* White dog beverage manager, Glen, when introduced to the DraughtMaster System was intrigued in what the system could potentially do to help aid the environment but was unsure of how this switch would help them save money, especially during such a difficult time like the Covid-19 Pandemic. Many businesses have already established relationships with local vendors as well as a system for recycling the kegs along and delivering them with a specific space set aside for them. Making these changes for a system that is not yet proven to do well with customers is a big risk considering all the added costs.

Along with the concern and risk of the added costs, consumers and business owners are skeptical of how the beer may taste in comparison to the beer in a traditional keg. Many are turned off by the word plastic in today's society because of how we have been conditioned to associate plastic with negative connotations. Carlsberg does have a great vision in what could be but he lacks key communication with customers of how the beer even holds up against the already established and loved keg system. We are talking about changing decades long of a system that works and in doing that there has to be a way to give complete confidence to those changing the system that the taste would hold up the same. This would go along with the earlier risk of added cost if the taste does not hold up the same and a business loses consumers because of it.

As mentioned earlier, our society is moving towards a plastic free life in order to help aid our environment that has been so negatively impacted by the material. When bringing up sustainability to business owners and consumers, plastic is the last word they thought they would hear in the same sentence. *"I really don't understand one aspect of this. Nowadays we are trying to distance ourselves from plastic, plastic straws are banned and now we want to exchange the barrel for plastic too? For me, this is not a particularly original path. Just why? Doesn't make sense to me."* This quote alone demonstrates how confused those are of what the

system is and how it would benefit the environment. There are even some doubts that the CO₂ emissions are less because of the machines needed for the recycling process as well as the production of plastic in the first place. Generally there is a lot of hesitation towards the system and more specifically the installation of said system, due to the fact that it involves the use of plastic. There is also a lack of information or long term research completed to help determine if this system is performing and delivering what Carlsberg says and to the point that can convince business owners to switch their system confidently.

Recommendations

Based on these findings from the research completed by all ten groups, recommendations can be made in relation to Carlsberg's strategy for expansion of the DraughtMaster system into the United States market. Since much of the skepticism that businesses and consumers had surrounding the DraughtMaster related to how well it would replace the traditional metal keg system, how it would affect the quality of the beer, and how sustainable the use of plastic is, the three following recommendations serve to resolve these key issues which may present obstacles to expansion into the U.S. market.

The first recommendation is for Carlsberg to provide guidelines for how the DraughtMaster system can be easily adopted by businesses, and an explanation of the benefits that come with replacing a traditional keg system with the DraughtMaster. From the B2B research it was found that many businesses were skeptical about the costs of replacing their current systems as well as the long term costs of maintenance. One of the research participants, a manager from Quakertown, PA, stated that most bars and *restaurants "have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating,"* and that the cost of bringing in a whole new system is a big risk. In order to address these concerns, Carlsberg needs to provide businesses with a clear long-term maintenance price comparison between the DraughtMaster and a traditional keg system. Included in this would be a cost estimate for the implementation of the DraughtMaster. This will be useful in getting businesses to switch to the DraughtMaster if it is shown that it can save money over time, and it also should not be a large cost for Carlsberg to conduct the price comparison.

The second recommendation is for Carlsberg to emphasize how the quality of the beer is unaltered by the DraughtMaster system and the use of plastic kegs. Several of the participants expressed concern regarding how the taste or quality of the beer may be affected by being stored in plastic, and confusion surrounding how the beer maintains its carbonation with a lack of CO₂. When proposing the DraughtMaster to businesses and consumers, Carlsberg needs to prove that the system does not affect the quality of the beer. One way of doing this would be to allow businesses a tasting trial of the DraughtMaster in which they can try the beer from the plastic keg and compare it to normal draft beer. A beverage director based in Philadelphia stated that being able to try the beer first would give him a better idea of how likely they would be to implement the DraughtMaster. While Carlsberg will have to account for the cost of giving out free trials or samples of the beer, it will be worth it in order to gain the trust of businesses.

Lastly, Carlsberg needs to obtain more long-term research on the environmental impact of the plastic keg system, and then clearly explain the findings to consumers through the use of advertising. Skepticism surrounding the use of plastic kegs was one of the biggest issues shown in the research. Since many businesses are working towards limiting the use of plastic within their work for environmental reasons, it seemed counterintuitive to many businesses and consumers to suggest switching to a plastic keg design in order to be more sustainable. When asked about the use of plastic, one participant stated, *"Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is really recycled."*

Though there is a baseline explanation for why the plastic keg is environmentally friendly in the sense that it saves water, can be recycled, and limits Co2 emissions, the widespread distaste for plastic will be a challenging hurdle to overcome. Therefore, Carlsberg must devote more focus to clearly explaining to consumers and businesses how the use of plastic is beneficial in the DraughtMaster system. First, there needs to be a clear comparison showing the environmental impact of a traditional keg to the plastic keg. For example, a big question which came up was if recycling the plastic kegs has a better environmental impact than reusing metal kegs. This information needs to be put in a format that will be easy for consumers to understand, such as in an infographic or an advertisement. Secondly, provide a simple explanation for how plastic can be sustainable, and what the long term impact of the kegs will be on the environment. Lastly, there needs to be more information on the recycling process of the plastic kegs. Many businesses were wondering if there would be any protocol to ensure that they really get recycled rather than just thrown away. The overall cost for this will have to account for the additional research into plastic sustainability and recycling, as well as the creation of materials to relay the information to consumers.

In conclusion, the DraughtMaster presents an innovative solution to the issue of making the draft beer industry more sustainable, however in order to incorporate the new system into the United States Carlsberg must overcome the main concerns of businesses and consumers such as how to implement it, the quality of the beer, and the perception of plastic. This can all be overcome by adopting the correlating recommendations, including providing more explanation of the system, allowing for trials before implementation of the DraughtMaster, and conducting more long-term research on sustainability comparisons to inform possible consumers. Once all these steps are taken, the DraughtMaster should be successful in the United States.

Group 8

Introduction

In this paper, we analyze whether and how Carlsberg should enter the US market with its DraughtMaster system. For this purpose, the "Drexel University" and the "Berlin School of Economics and Law" conducted a qualitative study. "The DraughtMaster is a complete beer delivery system that uses concepts from the so-called circular economy to operate. The goal of the DraughtMaster is to reduce environmental impact while also providing organizational efficiency. It contains two central innovations, the kegs are made of plastic instead of metal, and the CO2 gas component is replaced by another mechanism."

Our goal is to give Carlsberg a recommendation and to formulate conditions under which a market launch can succeed, so that this does not fail. Throughout our research we had the ability to ask very specific questions and receive very specific feedback across the board. Furthermore, we will show which additional criteria still need to be included and where Carlsberg needs further study data.

Methodology

Before we start with the actual results, this part is dedicated to the analysis, with the question of how we collected data, how we proceeded and why we chose the appropriate method.

Our project is a collaboration between Drexel University in Philadelphia and the Berlin School of Economics and Law. This intercultural cooperation is intended to ensure that experience from markets (Germany and the USA) can be incorporated into the project and that results can be recorded for specific market conditions. In order to be able to give Carlsberg recommendations, we have taken a qualitative research approach. This method has the decisive advantage that the industry can be better understood and that it is possible to talk to the participants in sufficient depth and thus test hypotheses. In contrast, quantitative approaches can provide less information about the background of the data, the participants reply. In conducting the research, we formed 10 different groups. Each of these groups conducted three different interviews. Two of them with B2C consumers (one person in the US and one in Germany) and one interview with a B2B representative (either from Germany or the US). For the B2B representative, we made sure that the person had enough experience in the restaurant industry (e.g. bar owner, manager). This was to ensure sufficient validity. (i.e. the absence of systematic errors due to unsuitable interview partners should be excluded). The questions were in-deep questions, if possible, no simple yes-no questions, but questions where the interviewee had to answer in detail. For both B2B and B2C, the questions focused on general attitudes toward beer and sustainability. In the case of consumers, however, the focus was on personal beer consumption, while in the case of B2B the focus was on the technical devices of the beer dispensing system and the supply chain. The goal here was to comprehensively find out how consumers and B2Bs feel about seamlessness in the beer industry. The questions were structured similar to an hourglass. At the beginning, the questions were very general (e.g., consumers were asked about their drinking habits) and then became more and more specific (e.g., what types of beverages are drunk and what is the attitude of B2B/B2C to sustainability). After that, the questions became more general again. In order to achieve sufficient reliability (free of random errors), all interviews of the 10 groups were included in the subsequent analysis. Thus, our qualitative analysis is based on a total of 30 interviews. For safety, all

interviews were recorded to avoid any ambiguities. Afterwards, all interviews were typed up in text. Each group then recorded the most important information from their interviews and made it available to all the other groups.

Findings

Through the method described above, we were able to distil five findings which in turn influence the recommendations for the market launch and which should therefore be included in the evaluation:

Finding 1: The Use of Plastic is Conflicting to Business Owners

Throughout the research and interview process, our findings have highlighted that the current DraughtMaster system is seen to have multiple drawbacks. Firstly, B2B consumers have a variety of concerns regarding the fact that the keg is plastic because of plastic waste and the difficulties in the recycling system. The use of plastic is conflicting due to the amount of time it takes to break down even when recycled. When interviewed, a waiter stated, *“Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is really recycled.”* In addition to the concern about whether plastic is actually more sustainable, there is a clear concern on how to recycle the system and if it's actually being done correctly. Business owners also mentioned that they don't necessarily connect plastic usage as being a positive aspect. One stated, *“I really don't understand one aspect of this. Nowadays we are trying to distance ourselves from plastic, plastic straws are banned and now we want to exchange the barrel for plastic too? For me, this is not a particularly original path. Just why? Doesn't make sense to me.”* Society in general is moving towards a plastic free lifestyle due to past negative impact by the material. Individuals feel conflicted about how beneficial it would really be to reintroduce it to their business. Business owners also questioned where the plastic goes after the keg is empty and if they would have to dispose of them themselves.

Additionally, we found that B2B consumers prefer reusing over recycling. The DraughtMaster is a single use system. There is a lack of knowledge of how the DraughtMaster gets recycled and if the process is actually effective. Overall, there is an uncertainty on the right disposal when the kegs become empty, questioning the true effectiveness of the system. Due to this, consumers expressed that they would be more inclined to stick to their traditional keg which is known to be reusable.

Finding 2: Sustainability Alone is not Enough for Business Owners

Although there is an importance of sustainability understood by consumers and the industry, sustainability alone is not enough for business owners to utilize the DraughtMaster System. In this industry, most consumers do not choose their beer to drink or bar to go to based on how sustainable it is. Customers don't care much about the draught system which is used. Most do not even care enough to ask or would not let this change which bar they go to. Business owners believe that the sustainability factor could potentially attract tourists but not enough to make a viable difference. We found that main paying points of customers include price, taste, and known branding. In terms of the taste, there is a concern for the change in taste and also a disquiet about the DraughtMaster actually tasting better enough to be worth switching to. Business owners and staff are hesitant to blindly switch over without knowing how consumers will react to the change in taste. Especially since this hasn't been an ongoing issue they've

noticed in the past. This mindset is also shown by the Director of Operations of a Berwyn PA bar that stated, *“if it ain’t broke, don’t fix it”* Business owners believe that their customers are already accustomed to the traditional system and the change is too big of a risk. Consumers come in to get regional beverages in which they prefer the taste and origin over how sustainable beer is drawn from a tap. They already know what they like and how much they’re willing to pay for it.

Finding 3: Business Owners are Concerned about Added Costs

There is also a worry of an added cost if the taste does not align to what individuals are used to. A business owner in Quakertown PA expressed that he would be open to the idea of switching but his main conflict would be cost. He expressed that most establishments already have keg rooms that they’ve invested loads of money on. Additionally, businesses currently already have well developed relationships with local vendors that they receive deliveries from. Acquiring a new system that is yet to be proven to do well with their customers is a huge risk that could be detrimental. For this reason, business owners are skeptical about making the switch until they’re able to first hand see the benefit in costs and customer reactions.

Finding 4: The German and US Market have Differentiating Needs

Overall, through our findings we were able to draw the conclusion that while draft beer is key for both markets, different markets have different concerns and pain points. Germany has many small businesses that focus on tradition. During our interviews, a German Business Owner stated *“I don’t know if the system is beneficial for Germany, we have a good reuse/recycling system of the aluminum barrels, combined with low transportation ways, due to local breweries and regional ingredients the old system is better for the environment.”* They prefer to serve local beer and prioritize taste over most other factors. Their customers value good, fresh tasting beer. These consumers also have very strong brand loyalty. Large beer producers serve mostly only big events in Germany. Due to this, a change in system would be a huge adjustment for this market. Whereas we found that the US market does not prioritize tradition as much. As much as there are well known beer brands, their consumers are much more open minded and willing to try something new. The US also does not have as good of a reuse system currently put into place so a sustainable option is definitely more of interest to business owners.

Recommendations

When going through our findings, it was evident that there are some steps that can be taken from the Carlsberg side to establish a better connection with the customer while also staying true to their own brand.

Recommendation 1: Use Direct comparison to attract customers

A lot of the DraughtMaster’s systems benefits are underwhelming when not directly compared to the current system the consumer is using. A way to show the customer the true benefits of this system would be to directly compare it to the current system. An efficient way to do this is by offering free testing to consumers so that they are able to establish for themselves whether the system is right for their business. Rather than telling the benefits, it would be more

beneficial to the company to show them in comparison to regular beer, for example they should make it clearer and more explicit that they pollute 40% less CO₂ than regular beer. Letting the customer get a free trial would in turn help them see the benefits both financially and in their own product of the difference between reusing and recycling and why recycling would be the better option for the environment.

Recommendation 2: Keep the switching costs low

Training their employees to learn how to remove the kegs or even clean them is an upfront cost that the owners have to pay in order to have their employees trained. According to our findings, a way for Carlsberg to make their system more beneficial for the customers would be to provide the training that is needed to use the DraughtMaster system free of cost. This would lead to lower switching costs, since the cost to train the employees has been taken out of the owners hands. Once the owner is confident that they don't have to incur an extra cost to train their employees, they would be more likely to use the DraughtMaster system compared to if the training was an expense that the owner would have to take on.

Recommendation 3: Focus on B2B Customers

The biggest focus for Draughtmaster right now should be with the B2B customers. Our analysis shows that customers don't care much about the draught system and their system would mostly be implemented with the B2B customers. The results and research show that they need to focus their distribution efforts on the B2B customers. Local pubs and breweries in the US would be more susceptible and accepting to using a system like DraughtMaster because there isn't really a regional beer culture where most pubs get their beer from a regional brewery like there is in countries in Europe i.e. Germany, England. Also, as our research shows, the customers in the American market that these businesses get aren't usually as traditional with their take on beer and are already used to the big brands like Carlsberg, AB etc.

Recommendation 4: Different approaches for Different markets

Staying linear with their approach to their product is important for Carlsberg, but where they should diversify their efforts is to try and develop different advertisements and outlooks when trying to enter different markets and for different target groups. Highlighting the right aspect of their system when entering a market that cares more about the sustainability aspect than the ease of installation can be important and vice versa. This would lead to a more varied presence and more room for developing their products vision while also catering to each of different customers needs.

In conclusion, as mentioned previously the goal of our research was to attempt to be able to give recommendations for the start of bringing DraughtMaster to the US. What we took you through was an in depth look at what it takes in order to come up with those recommendations. Which are keeping the cost low for customers, focusing on B2B customers, showing the benefits in a direct opposite system to the current system, and having different advertisements for different markets. Each of these recommendations were founded by using extensive qualitative research, and each of them must be things the marketing team looks at when figuring out how to implement the DraughtMaster in the US. Our final recommendation is that Carlsberg should enter the market in the US, but have to do more research, because our

research can't provide all the insights. For example, we did not have quantitative data on the general competitive situation and market share, as well as price levels. In addition, Carlsberg should consider our recommendations, especially the focus on B2B customers in marketing, since B2C customers have too little interest in the actual supply and beer tap method.

Group 9

Introduction

Over the past few weeks, our class has collaborated with students from Berlin's School of Economics and Law to learn more about the DraughtMaster. The DraughtMaster brings a unique and sustainable beer keg to bars, restaurants, and breweries to serve on tap. With a reduction of CO2 emissions and ease of implementation with over 500 beers; this product could easily change the way people view the beer industry forever. We were tasked with determining whether the DraughtMaster would be a profitable and feasible product if launched in the United States. We conducted multiple qualitative surveys to provide Carlsberg with the insight on whether implementing the DraughtMaster would be worth it in the United States.

Methodology

We were split up into ten groups, consisting of students from both Drexel University and the Berlin School of Economics and Law. Each group conducted three interviews to learn what different consumers and businesses thought of the DraughtMaster and how it could be implemented. We conducted two qualitative interviews with consumers of beer, with one consumer being in the United States and the other consumer in Germany. We also conducted one interview with a business who sells beer on tap in the country of our choosing. In total, we ended up with interviews from ten consumers in the United States, ten consumers in Germany, five businesses in the United States, and five businesses in Germany.

With the consumers, we asked questions pertaining to what their typical drinking habits are, like whether they go to bars, drink at home etc. We also asked them what they think of sustainability and how/if they incorporate sustainable practices into their daily lives. We then showed them the DraughtMaster system and how it works and asked what they thought about it and if it would affect any of their drinking habits. With the businesses, we asked questions about what their current process of serving beer on tap looks like and if they have an issue with it, how the consumer/business owner felt regarding sustainability as a whole and incorporating it into the workplace, what they thought of the DraughtMaster's functionality and what they liked or disliked about it as well as any problems they could see with implementing it.

We chose to do qualitative research because we needed to understand the thoughts behind these consumers, not just the numbers of people who would agree. Asking more thought-provoking questions helped us understand our customer demographic, what they like and dislike, and help us better analyze our results. We were able to take the transcripts of thirty interviews and go through them to find some major takeaways of what issues could arise from trying to bring the DraughtMaster into the United States.

Findings

When we began our analysis, a huge point of conflict we found, specifically with businesses that would be incorporating the new technology, was the pricing of the DraughtMaster. The

general manager of a restaurant in Quakertown, PA with eighteen rotating taps stated, *“I know, restaurants would definitely like to know what that cost would be up front. Because a lot of them don't necessarily have room for a lot of new equipment. Or they have keg rooms that they've already spent all of this money on creating”*. They also compared selling Carlsberg beer for about five dollars a pint to other premium beers that they sell for eight or nine dollars a pint. Since Carlsberg beer is not typically able to sell at a premium price in the States, it would be difficult for the benefits of using the DraughtMaster to outweigh the upfront cost of bringing in a whole new system to many restaurants and bars that already operate on very thin margins. This shows us that one major implication of bringing the DraughtMaster to the United States would be proving that the upfront cost that the DraughtMaster brings these restaurants and breweries would be worth it because of all the advantages it would bring to the places and the environment. There is little to no information on pricing on the DraughtMaster website, leaving the consumers with lots of questions regarding what the price for a system like this would look like.

After analyzing the class's results, the consensus is that restaurant and bar owners liked the idea of sustainability. Although they understand the need to be sustainable, the cost of being environmentally friendly deters them from moving toward a sustainable model. Most restaurants view beer as a non-priority and would be the least willing to implement the DraughtMaster. The restaurant model makes it incredibly difficult to implement more sustainable practices especially after COVID-19 with the new safety regulations. For example, restaurants that used to use reusable, stainless steel cutlery and washable cloths have now decided to entirely switch over to plastic sealed paper napkins and plastic utensils (Hartke 2020). The CDC has recommended that people choose to order take out which involves much more waste than in comparison to a sit down setting where a restaurant may be able to use reusable plates and cups (CDC 2021). Not only does the CDC instill more regulations which makes reusable objects harder to use, but there is also the dilemma of the public being afraid to use objects that were touched by others even if the restaurant or bar claims to have thoroughly washed the utensils. The restaurant and bar industry has been faced with this challenge of needing to prioritize their customer's safety first in terms of minimizing germs spread. However, it has led to eco-friendly practices being pushed to the side. As a result, when we spoke about DraughtMaster to a restaurateur, they received the message pleasantly because they were curious to see how beer could be more sustainable despite the thousands of gallons of water waste in kegs.

DraughtMaster aims to be a sustainable solution to the beer industry, but they replace a metal keg with a plastic keg. In the United States, businesses did not see a conflict with the plastic keg because most businesses agreed that the plastic usability in a circular economy justified the plastic component. An American B2B made the comment, *“restaurants and bars are not sustainable, so anything would be a step up from the current system we have running even if that included plastic.”* However, various German businesses believed that they were already doing a good job with their sustainable practices. A German B2B quoted, *“I don't know if the system is beneficial for Germany, we have a good reuse/recycling system of the aluminum barrels, combined with low transportation ways, due to local breweries and regional ingredients the old system is better for the environment.”* As a result, German businesses had many issues with DraughtMaster because of the potential harm of microplastics and distrust with the validity of the recycling process of the plastic kegs.

The final discovery we made was the concern with the DraughtMaster's product design and whether it will be more helpful to the environment. The DraughtMaster prides itself on its recyclable aspects and we saw that people liked this feature. Your typical keg is not always reusable, and with old beer and CO₂ pumped throughout it, they usually end up in landfills. DraughtMaster claims that with plastic containers, they are better for the planet because they

are recyclable and produce less waste. According to their website, *“DraughtMaster is 43% lighter than traditional kegs...All this reduced weight means that delivery vehicles are using less fuel to deliver the same quantity of beer. Less fuel = less CO2.”* While the sustainability aspect of the actual keg is beneficial, we found that a few business owners and employees were still skeptical of the extent to which the kegs can be recycled. Typically, plastics that are going to be recycled need to be empty and dry, so business owners will now need to be responsible for that before recycling the kegs. A server interviewed in Germany had the following opinion, *“Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends on if the plastic is really recycled.”* According to an article from National Geographics in 2019, a new study in the peer-reviewed journal Science Advances, is the first global analysis of all plastics ever made... 8.3 billion metric tons have been produced, 6.3 billion metric tons have become plastic waste... only nine percent has been recycled. Most of the plastic ends up in the ocean, contaminating water and harming ecosystems. It is fair to be concerned that the plastic will not be properly recycled especially without knowing exactly where the kegs end up. Other business owners were concerned with the fact that they know how people are, and they would not be careful with the plastic kegs. There are still more questions to be answered, such as are the kegs fragile, and can they still be recycled if they become damaged?

Recommendations

To tackle some of the pricing issues that came up from the business-to-business interviews, we have come up with two recommendations. A good starting point could be having a “build your own” system page on their website, like how you can build your own car on a car manufacturer's website. This would be the closest way for business owners or managers to see what the DraughtMaster system would look like without seeing it physically in person. They would also have all the upfront costs available for them to see. We believe that another good option would be to offer a sixty-day money back guarantee, so that businesses can take this system and try it out. They would be able to try out all the digital tracking, see how the beers sell, and talk to their customers to see how they like it since Carlsberg claims better tasting beer. This would take away the fear of investing all this upfront cost and for it not to work in their favor. The advantages of the kegs like being lighter/easier to handle and possibly saving them money with less wasting since it stays fresh longer, may sway them to keep the system. You need to get the system into actual businesses and show them how it would work to their benefit. Many of the businesses are hesitant because they feel they don't need to change what's not broken in the establishments, but Carlsberg will need to convince their customers if they want to successfully bring the DraughtMaster into the United States.

While all products may be great and bring value to a consumer's life, unless there is proper marketing for the new product, profits will be hard to come by. As we learned through our research, consumers primarily drink beer for the entertainment aspect. When it comes to ordering a drink at a bar, beach, or a social event... sustainability isn't always the first thing that comes to their mind. For the DraughtMaster, we recommend that budgets will need to be set aside for marketing, as they should partner with other sustainable beer companies like Carlsberg including Finnegan's. As Finnegan's is a brewery that gives “100% of the profits from the beer business to projects that tackle poverty and hunger” ([Global Shakers](#)). We believe this partnership would support the idea that Finnegan's and the DraughtMaster not only care about the environment, but as individuals themselves. We also are advocating that the DraughtMaster and selected beer companies should also create a social media campaign that would give back a certain percentage to other green companies and nonprofits to spread awareness. With social media being a hotspot for people to post their selfies and pictures from nights out, it made sense to us that doing a social media campaign for the DraughtMaster would make the most

sense. In our B2C interview with an avid beer drinker we found that, “drinking beer means [they’re] having a good time... with friends” (B2C Interview Transcript). This campaign would be conducted that every time a user on Instagram shares a photo under the hashtag #KeepCoolWithCarlsberg \$0.25 cents will be donated to a green company: with a limit of \$150,000. This campaign will run during the month of February, during the Super Bowl, as this time is filled with partying and socializing with friends. To further this idea of a social media campaign, long-term (when budgets allow) partnerships could occur with the NFL and football teams who share the mindset of going green and giving back to their community.

Wrapping things up, our group feels strongly that Carlsberg beer could benefit from the DraughtMaster, however it is not feasible at the time. With a high price tag for this transition, we believe people are not putting beer drinking and sustainability at the forefront of their minds. At the end of the day, people are going to drink beer whether it was produced sustainably or not. If sustainability were to become more important to the beer industry, this may be something that could continue to be talked about and then later down the road, taking more of an initiative to implement.

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Group 10

Introduction

Carlsberg Group, one of the largest beer companies in the world. The company's innovation of Draughtmaster differs from the traditional beer delivery system. Instead, it reduces environmental impact by replacing the traditional metal keg with a plastic keg, while implementing the concepts of the circular economy. The use of the Draughtmaster brings the benefits of easier handling of the kegs during the delivery and shipment process. As well as, better sustainable practices for businesses such as recycling, and preserving the quality of the beer for a longer period of time. The system has been launched in European countries, so the question lies in whether the system should also be launched in the United States. Students from Berlin School of Economics and Law and Drexel University have collaborated together to answer the question through primary research. In the following paper, students from Drexel will talk about the methodology used to conduct the research question, findings found during the research, and recommendations for Carlsberg in their future launch in the US market.

Methodology

The methodology used to conduct our primary research are interviews, specially dividing into business to consumer and business to business. In this project, we conducted an interview with one B2C interviewee from Germany and one B2C interviewee from the US. After talking to consumers, we later interviewed our B2B interviewee. For our two B2C interviewees, we interviewed a college student from Philadelphia and a college student from Berlin. We specially chose to interview the two individuals because they are beer drinkers and have some knowledge about the different types of beer brands. The interviews were conducted via Zoom Meetings, both lasting approximately 20-25 minutes. Prior to the B2C interviews, we made interview guidelines, asking questions regarding interviewee's general information and general questions on the topic such as what is the individual's preference when choosing beer. Concept testing questions like asking whether the individual likes the plastic based system and how do they feel about implementing this idea in Europe vs the US. During the interview with the B2C interviewee, questions regarding sustainable practices were asked as well. After the interview, we transcribed the interview audio and analyzed the responses received from our interviewee.

In our B2B interview, we followed the same steps of writing an interview transcript, conducting the interview, then analyzing the results. Our interviewee is from Berlin and is a deputy manager of a sole proprietor fish restaurant. The interviewee serves beer on tap and specifies that tap beer is something that locals and tourists prefer over bottled beer. She was also familiar with Draughtmaster before we introduced her to the system. In this one on one interview, we were able to receive responses and discover new findings and opinions regarding Draughtmaster from Germany's side. Similar to the B2C interview questions, we asked about the individual's general information as well as sustainability questions such as:

- *“Why is it important to you to include sustainable practices in your business?”*

General questions regarding their business were also asked. Those include:

- *“What kinds of beer do you sell?”*

- *“How do you handle tap beer and the system of kegs? How is it reflected in your restaurant infrastructure?”*

Some concepts questions asked were:

- *“How do you like this idea about a plastic based system to fight pollution and benefit the environment? Are you comfortable using it?”*
- *“If implemented the Draughtmaster system, what types of changes would be necessary for the system?”*

With our interview with the B2B interviewee, we were able to capture some of the positive and negative thoughts on the implementation of the plastic keg systems for the German business. One thought mentioned by the interviewee is that Draughtmaster “is nice, but the keg design is a bit complicated, so I would prefer sticking to the traditional kegs.” (response from interview)

After gathering our interviews, we combined over 30 different interviews with the whole class and analyzed them using a spreadsheet. Through this type of data gathering and analyzing, we were able to break down the interview transcripts easily, review other team’s interviews, and receive feedback from other teams. After analyzing and peer reviews, the last part of our research was presenting our key findings and recommendations to the whole class. More details about our findings and recommendations for Draughtmaster will be talked about further in this paper.

Findings

Our group interviewed consumers from both Philadelphia and Berlin, as well as a restaurant that sells beer in Berlin that could potentially benefit from replacing their current system with the Draughtmaster. One of the main concerns that was brought up in both sessions was on sustainability and how plastic kegs are supposed to be more environmentally friendly than metal ones. Among the Draughtmaster’s selling points is the fact that the design is meant to decrease CO2 emissions, however, plastic waste is a major concern amongst consumers. When asked about their opinion on single-use plastic, our consumer interviewee replied, “[I] use less plastic and try to not buy stuff that is packed in plastic.” This perception of plastic usage is shared amongst both German and American consumers, which can be a concern to Carlsberg when trying to expand into other regions in the world.

In addition, our German business interviewee had questions on how to properly dispose of empty Draughtmaster kegs and suggested that Carlsberg teach their employees new recycling practices to effectively recycle or reuse the kegs. They also argued that metal kegs are more sustainable because they can be reused, whereas each Draughtmaster keg can only be used once and contrastingly recycled. The business mentioned that they have steered away from the use of plastic materials in general and would be hesitant to switch to a new product that could potentially hurt their ideal branding image.

“There’s a reason that they’ve [beer kegs] been made of metal for so long.” (Interview B2B Berlin)

Furthermore, the general finding from our interview with our B2B contact in Berlin is that there is not enough consumer demand for them to switch their current keg system over to the Draughtmaster.

“I think there would be some people that would be interested in it and that would make a decision like if you provided both, you said one sustainable and one is regular, I think

some people would go to sustainable one. But generally, most people who drink beer go about the brand.” (Interview B2B Berlin)

Recommendations

Our recommendation to address consumer and business questions over sustainability practices is to implement a company-sponsored recycling program. We suggest Carlsberg allow businesses to return used kegs for them to recycle. This exchange can be done simultaneously as the company is distributing new kegs via shipments, thus minimizing any extra steps in the supply chain. Whether it be to repurpose the plastic to make new kegs or to make other products or to simplify the disposal process for business owners, this program would help address the concern about the use of plastic over metal kegs.

Another recommendation directly from our BSB interviewee would be for Carlsberg to provide information on how to properly dispose of plastic kegs if a recycling program as described above is not feasible.

“ I think if the company provides enough information on how to do it, actually, I don't think it would be a big problem. I think most of the problems with like separating stuff is that people don't know how to do it.” (Interview B2B Berlin)

Our group believes that by implementing these initiatives, as well as equipping businesses with the necessary information and marketing materials to educate consumers about the benefits of the Draughtmaster, Carlsberg can create enough consumer demand for these businesses to make the switch.

In conclusion, The Draughtmaster, an innovative plastic beer keg created by Carlsberg Group is aimed at being sustainable by reducing CO2 emissions, being easier to recycle, as well as preserving the quality of beer for a longer period of time has raised the question from consumers and business if the product would work well if launched in the US. From all of the interviews we conducted including a B2C consumer in the US, B2C consumer in Berlin, as well as a B2B deputy manager of a sole proprietor fish restaurant, we were able to provide some critical recommendations from comments and feedback from our interviewees. One finding we had revolved around consumers and the business don't think the plastic kegs are sustainable since although one of Draughtmaster's selling points is not having CO2 emissions, there were concerns from our interviewees about plastic waste. To remedy this, our recommendation was addressing consumer and business questions about sustainability as well as implementing a company-sponsored recycling program. This should be relatively easy for Carlsberg to implement as the exchange for old and new kegs can be simultaneously done to justify any supply chain concerns. Another finding we had was interviewees concerns, especially B2C for the size and shape of the plastic Draughtmaster kegs. A smaller size can mean that businesses would have shipments too often and would have to switch out the keg more often because it is smaller compared to the traditional metal keg. Space usage was another concern with the shape of Draughtmaster's keg since it might not be optimal. A recommendation for this issue is for Carlsberg to have various size options so depending on consumer demand for a business, they can choose accordingly.

B2C concerns also came up regarding the taste of beer. The interviewees were big fans of beer and taste was definitely a strong seller and point for them to critique on for the Draughtmaster as it is a plastic keg and not metal. A recommendation we came up with for Carlsberg was to focus on the marketing around the taste not being impacted and also pointing out that the beer

actually remains fresher for longer periods of time than the traditional metal keg since CO2 is not used. Considering all of the potential resistance factors of utilizing the Draughtmaster and bringing it to the US, we still see a lot of positives from interviewees about the product and the recommendations to improve on concerns relatively easy to pursue. Since a sustainable plastic keg like the Draughtmaster is a new product penetrating an old traditional metal keg market, concerns are not surprising, and are common.

Concluding remarks

The Carlsberg DraughtMaster system represents an innovative leap toward sustainability in the draft beer industry. However, the path to U.S. market acceptance requires overcoming skepticism about the use of plastic, concerns about beer quality, and the financial implications of transitioning to this new system. While European markets have already embraced this technology, American businesses and consumers are cautious, requiring transparent communication, robust support, and compelling evidence that taste and quality remain intact.

While Carlsberg's success in the U.S. hinges on addressing these key concerns through strategic marketing and education, some concerns linger on the plastic waste from the German. By emphasizing the long-term environmental benefits, debunking myths surrounding plastic recycling, and offering cost-effective adoption solutions, the company can shift perceptions. After all, sustainability is not just a trend; it's a necessity for the future of the brewing industry. With the right approach, DraughtMaster can lead this transformation, proving that great beer and a greener planet can go hand-in-hand.